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1. | Executive Summary

This report assesses the impact of the **EU-EMBRACES (Empowering Minds: Boosting Research in Citizen Engagement and Schools)** project throughout its full duration (M1, May 2024–M20, December 2025). EU-EMBRACES aimed to foster public engagement in science, promote inclusivity, and bridge socio-economic gaps in accessing scientific knowledge. The evaluation focuses on outreach activities, audience engagement, and researcher participation, using a combination of surveys, reports, and observational data.

This is the **final impact assessment report**, and includes all the collected data, since the start of the project.

A total of **300 events** were organized (111 in 2024 and 189 in 2025), including **63 build-up events** (32 in 2024 and 31 in 2025), **18 European Researchers' Night (ERN) events** (9 in each edition), **158 Meet the Scientists sessions** (57 in 2024 and 101 in 2025), **18 participatory debates** (one of which in 2024), **39 Social Inclusion through Science and Technology** activities (12 in 2024 and 27 in 2025), and **4 science communication workshops within the ERN Youth Ambassadors Program**, engaging **over 57,300 participants**. Notably, **25% of all surveyed participants** had their first direct interaction with a scientist, reflecting the project's success in reaching new audiences. Additionally, **2,215 researchers** contributed to the initiative, with **11% having no prior public engagement experience**.

Efforts to reach underserved communities were a key priority, with **39 activities specifically targeting underserved neighborhoods and TEIP** (Territórios Educativos de Intervenção Prioritária/Educational Territories of Priority Intervention) **schools with historically high dropout rates and retention challenges**, contributing to the project's broader inclusivity goals. In total, **7,222 students** aged 6 to 17 participated in initiatives designed to enhance access to science education, including programs in schools with socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds.

The impact assessment revealed high satisfaction levels with the activities, with **92% giving a positive feedback (4 or 5)** and **60% of respondents giving the highest rating** and no negative feedback.

Data collection efforts were strengthened through a centralized approach across multiple venues, but challenges remain in increasing researcher survey participation, particularly at large-scale events.

Overall, the results indicate that the project has successfully achieved its intended objectives—and even surpassed some targets set—fully aligning with its mission to enhance science communication, engage diverse and new audiences, and involve researchers in outreach activities.

Notably, activities held in **schools** and in **peripheral urban areas** reached the **highest shares of new audiences** and participants with limited prior exposure to science, at **29%** and **33%**, respectively. European Researchers' Night (ERN) events also succeeded in reaching new publics, although to a lesser extent: **18%** of participants reported that this was their first contact with a scientist. Overall, ERN audiences still tend to be more highly educated and more strongly connected to science than the general population.

At the same time, large-scale events with high public participation—such as ERN and its build-up initiatives—are those where the proportion of researchers taking part in outreach activities for the *first time* is highest. This confirms the crucial role of these flagship events in encouraging researchers to engage in outreach.

2. | Introduction

2.1. Background of the EU-EMBRACES

The EU-EMBRACES (Empowering Minds: Boosting Research in Citizen Engagement and Schools) project, funded by Horizon Europe, was a 20-month initiative implemented during 2024–2025. Its overarching aim was to foster engagement and inclusivity in science communication, with a particular focus on addressing socio-economic inequalities in access to science and innovation. By actively involving communities that do not typically participate in science-related activities, as well as underrepresented groups—particularly those from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds—EU-EMBRACES sought to demonstrate the positive impact of the Horizon Europe Missions on everyday life.

Alongside two editions of the **European Researchers' Night** (ERN), implemented across nine venues in continental Portugal, the project delivered a diverse set of complementary activities. These included meetings between researchers and

students in schools located in both small towns and major urban centres (**Meet the Scientists Programme**); **participatory debates** for students on topics related to the European Missions; outreach initiatives in underserved neighbourhoods and in schools with historically high dropout rates (**Social Inclusion through Science and Technology**); the **ERN Youth Ambassadors Programme**; and a series of public-space activities -implemented in a wide range of locations and through highly diverse formats- designed to build momentum in the lead-up to the ERN events (**build-up activities**).

2.2 Objectives

The main objectives of the EU-EMBRACES project were designed to create a lasting change in the way science is communicated and how underrepresented groups engage with it. These objectives served as the foundation for measuring the project's success in fostering inclusivity and public engagement.

The six key objectives were:

1. **Increase awareness of science and scientific careers;**
2. **Reach new audiences and underserved communities;**
3. **Promote public engagement with science, particularly through participatory activities;**
4. **Involve scientists in science communication activities;**
5. **Showcase EU-funded projects and Portuguese research institutions;**
6. **Organize high-quality outreach activities.**

2.3 Expected Impact

By achieving its objectives, the project aimed to generate both **short-term** and **long-term impacts**.

Short-term impacts included:

- Delivery of over 250 activities and events that engage both researchers and non-expert audiences, particularly young people and underserved groups.
- Creation of a Youth Ambassadors network of at least 40 students across the country to foster youth involvement and competences in science communication.

- Widespread citizen participation across the country in science outreach activities.
- Active involvement of researchers from diverse scientific fields in public outreach.
- Increased visibility of EU Missions and EU-funded research projects.
- Greater visibility for research institutions and their work.

Mid-term impacts focus on a shift in engagement patterns and attitudes:

- Increased engagement with science among the general population, particularly targeting underserved groups such as ethnic minorities, migrants, and socio-economically disadvantaged communities.
- Broader participation in science outreach activities of students who may see science as more approachable, opening pathways for future academic and research careers.
- Enhanced communication skills for researchers, allowing them to connect better with non-expert audiences and gaining insights into public concerns.
- Research centers and universities recognizing the importance of outreach beyond traditional audiences and considering new strategies to reach underserved groups.

Long-term impacts aim to produce societal, scientific, and economic changes:

- A more open and inclusive society where meaningful conversations can occur between researchers and citizens, fostering trust in science and the consideration of public perspectives in scientific discourse.
- Empowerment of future generations, equipped with critical and scientific thinking skills, to drive forward innovation and scientific inquiry.
- Promotion of open science, allowing research to be shared with the public and other stakeholders (e.g., industry, policymakers), encouraging the use of scientific results.
- Enhanced job opportunities and career paths in STEM fields for underserved groups, as well as fostering innovation to address societal challenges (e.g., climate change, cancer, sustainability).

These objectives and impacts were evaluated through key indicators and ongoing assessment throughout the project's duration.

2.4 Scope and structure of the report

This report presents the methodology used to assess the impact of the EU-EMBRACES project, focusing on data collection, evaluation tools, and key findings across the entire implementation period, particularly regarding public engagement, researcher involvement, and communication efforts.

The report is structured as follows:

- **Section 3** details the assessment methodology and tools, including ethical considerations;
- **Section 4** summarizes the activities evaluated, categorized by type;
- **Section 5** presents key findings and results of the project;
- **Section 6** discusses challenges and limitations in data collection and impact measurement;
- Finally, **Section 7** provides conclusions and recommendations for future editions, followed by **Appendices** containing assessment tools used in the evaluation.

3. | Methodology

3.1 Evaluation Approach: rationale for the assessment methodology

Within the overarching framework of fostering engagement and inclusivity in science communication, the six project objectives were grouped according to their primary focus: three objectives emphasized **public participation** in science communication events (Objectives 1, 2 and 3); one objective focused on the **active involvement of researchers** in outreach activities (Objective 4); another aimed to enhance the visibility of **research, EU policies** (Horizon Europe Missions), and **EU-funded projects** (Objective 5); and the final objective concerned the delivery of **high-quality outreach** activities (Objective 6).

In line with these priorities, the impact assessment methodology targeted **three key stakeholder groups: event participants, researchers, and event organisers**. The evaluation sought to characterise the events, the audiences involved, and the

participating researchers, while assessing the effects of these activities on both the public and the researchers.

Impact, even in the short term, extends beyond what can be fully captured through surveys and structured reporting tools. The mere occurrence of an event constitutes a form of impact in itself, even when collecting direct feedback from participants is not feasible. For this reason, the assessment also incorporated indirect evidence, such as photographs, observational notes, and personal testimonies.

Communication and dissemination activities formed another central dimension of the project's impact. These included outreach campaigns, media coverage, social media engagement, and the project's overall ability to attract interest and participation from diverse audiences. Evaluating the effectiveness of these efforts was essential for assessing the extent to which the project achieved its objectives and generated broader awareness.

Accordingly, in addition to the specific assessment tools designed for this purpose, the evaluation incorporated data related to event organisation and communication actions carried out throughout the project.

Finally, it is acknowledged that certain impacts -particularly those of a long-term nature- are inherently difficult to measure within the timeframe of the project. Where relevant, these limitations have been taken into account when interpreting the results.

3.2 Assessment Tools Developed and Implemented

To characterize the events, the participating audiences, and the involved researchers, while also evaluating the impact of these activities on both the public and the researchers, we established **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** accompanied by specific questions tailored to the three stakeholder groups. Based on these KPIs, we developed a suite of tools to collect both quantitative and qualitative data.

These tools included **surveys** (both paper-based and online) directed at participating members of the public and researchers; **voting walls**, such as dot-mocracy and post-it walls, or **show-of-hands voting** aimed at participants; **short activity reports** completed by event organizers through online forms, which also gathered collected **testimonies, observational notes, and photographs**.

The table below provides an overview of each project objective and its associated impacts, categorised into short-term and mid-term outcomes. It also identifies the KPIs defined to evaluate these impacts and specifies the data sources (in bold), along with the complementary tools and questions used to assess each KPI.

Although the project has now concluded, the expected long-term impacts—relating to societal, scientific, and economic changes—fall outside the timeframe of this evaluation. For this reason, they are not included in the table.

Table 1 - Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and information sources used to assess the impact of each project objective

Objective	Impact	KPI	KPI Source & additional insight
1. Increase awareness of science and scientific careers;	Short- term: Over 250 activities and events that engage both researchers and non-expert audiences, particularly young people and underserved groups.	# of events organized # of actions specifically with young people # of participants in the activities % of young participants in ERN	Activity reports from organizers Survey to participants: - <i>What surprised me the most was that...</i> - <i>I didn't know and now I know that...</i> Post-it walls: - <i>Three words you associate with science.</i> - <i>What do you consider the greatest challenge in science today?</i> - <i>In your daily life, where do you</i>

			<p><i>encounter science?</i></p> <p><i>- What is your main source of scientific information?</i></p> <p>Dotmocracy:</p> <p><i>- Scientists strive to inform society about new discoveries. (Yes, somewhat, no)</i></p> <p><i>- Scientific research is influenced by cultural and social factors. (Yes, I don't know, no)</i></p> <p><i>- What do you consider the greatest challenge in science today?</i></p>
	<p>Mid-term:</p> <p>Broader participation in science outreach activities of students who may see science as more approachable, opening pathways for future</p>	<p>#of events within Meet the Scientist campaign</p> <p># of students involved</p>	<p>Activity reports from teachers</p> <p>Informations from consortium partners</p> <p>Survey to students:</p> <p><i>- Do you think you could become a scientist?</i></p>

	academic and research careers.		<p>- I didn't know, but in this session, I learned...</p> <p>- Was there anything that surprised you during this interaction? What was it?</p>
2. Reach new audiences and underserved communities;	<p>Short term:</p> <p>Over 250 activities and events that engage both researchers and non-expert audiences, particularly young people and underserved groups.</p> <p>Many citizens across the country participating in science outreach activities;</p>	<p>Geographical distribution of events across the country</p> <p># of participants in the activities</p> <p>% of public that contacted with scientists for the first time</p> <p>Characterization of new publics</p> <p>#of actions specifically with students</p>	<p>Activity reports from organizers</p> <p>Survey to participants (ERN, Researchers at Schools):</p> <p>Characterization of the public (<i>age, gender, postal code, Level of education; professional status; mother's level of education</i>)</p> <p>- Was this the first time you contacted a scientist directly?</p> <p>- Do you usually participate in science events or festivals?</p> <p>- What is your mother's level of education?</p>
	<p>Mid term:</p> <p>Increased engagement with science among the general population, particularly targeting underserved groups such as</p>	<p># of students involved</p> <p># of students that contacted with scientists for the first time</p> <p>#of action specifically with underserved</p>	

	<p>ethnic minorities, migrants, and socio-economically disadvantaged populations</p> <p>Broader participation in science outreach activities of students who may see science as more approachable, opening pathways for future academic and research careers.</p>	<p>audiences;</p> <p># of activities in unserved neighborhoods and TEIP schools</p>	<p>- <i>What is your connection to science?</i></p> <p>Survey to students (Researchers at Schools):</p> <p>Characterization of the students (<i>grade level, school, gender, mother's level of education</i>)</p> <p>- <i>Was this the first time you directly interacted with a scientist?</i></p> <p>- <i>Do you think you could become a scientist?</i></p> <p>- <i>Have you participated in other science-related activities (outside of school)?</i></p> <p><i>Could someone like you become a scientist?</i></p> <p>Activity reports from organizers (activities in underserved the neighborhoods):</p> <p>- <i>Did you receive support from any neighborhood</i></p>
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			<p>structure or person/entity working in the neighborhood?</p> <p>- Was it important for the success of the event?</p>
3. Promote public engagement with science, particularly through participatory activities;	Short term: Creation of a Youth Ambassadors network of at least 40 students across the country to foster youth involvement and competences in science communication.	# of Youth Ambassadors involved in the program # of Ciência Viva club involved	Activity reports from organizers
	Mid-term: 15 participatory debates, involving at least 800 students	# of participatory debates organized # of students involved in the debates	Activity reports from organizers Survey to students: <p>- Do you feel that your opinion was important to the conclusions of the debate?</p>
4. Involve scientists in science communication activities;	Short-term: Active involvement of researchers from diverse scientific fields in public outreach.	#of researchers involved diversity of scientific areas involved	Survey to scientists: Characterization of researchers involved (Age, gender, Field of Scientific Activity, Professional Category)

	<p>Mid term:</p> <p>Enhanced communication skills for researchers, allowing them to connect better with non-expert audiences and gaining insights into public concerns.</p>	<p>% of scientists with no prior interaction with the public</p>	<p>Survey to scientists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Have you participated in science communication activities like this one (direct interaction with the public) before?</i> - <i>Do you feel that your participation was rewarding for you?</i> - <i>Positive aspects of the activity?</i> - <i>Challenges you encountered?</i> - <i>How would you describe the students/non-expert audience you interacted with in this session/event?</i>
	<p>Mid-term:</p> <p>Research centers and universities recognizing the importance of outreach beyond traditional audiences and considering new</p>	<p># of research institution involved</p> <p># of institutions that announced their participation in ERN through media platforms (websites, social media,...)</p>	<p>Information from partners</p> <p>Survey to scientists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Have you participated in science communication activities like this</i>

	strategies to reach underserved groups.	% of scientists that often participate in outreach activities	<i>one (direct interaction with the public) before?</i>
5. Showcase EU-funded projects and Portuguese research institutions;	Short-term: EU Missions highlighted;	% of activities in which EU missions were highlighted	Activity reports for organizers: <i>- Horizon Europe Mission addressed in the session (if applicable)</i> Dot-mocracy: <i>- Which of the European Commission's missions should receive more funding?</i>
	Short-term: EU funded project highlighted.	# of scientists funded by EU projects # of participating projects funded by the EU;	Information from partners Dot-mocracy: <i>- I knew that the European Commission funds Portuguese scientific projects. (Agree, Don't agree)</i>
	Short-term: Greater visibility for research institutions and their work.	# of institutions involved	Information from partners

<p>6. Organize high-quality outreach activities.</p>		<p>Satisfaction level</p>	<p>Survey to participants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rate your level of satisfaction with the event from 1 (not satisfied at all) to 5 (completely satisfied). - What did you like the most? - What could be improved? - I didn't know and now I know that... <p>Survey to students:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rate your level of satisfaction with the session from 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied); - What did you like most? - What do you think could be improved? <p>Survey to scientists:</p>
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			<p>- From the perspective of your participation, highlight challenges you encountered or aspects that could be improved.</p>
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3.3 Ethical principles

The EU-EMBRACES project adheres to high ethical standards in the design and administration of impact assessment tools. These tools, including surveys targeting participants and scientists, are guided by principles that ensure **voluntary participation, anonymity, confidentiality, and transparency regarding the objectives** of the data collection process.

Each survey begins with an explanatory introduction, clearly outlining the voluntary nature of participation, the guarantee of anonymity and confidentiality, and the purpose of the questions. To proceed, participants are required to provide explicit consent, which is the only mandatory question included in the surveys.

For online surveys, platforms such as Google Forms are used to collect responses without storing participants' contact information, ensuring data protection. Additionally, participants are provided with contact details for the project team should they have any questions or require further clarification.

In face-to-face contexts, whether the surveys are completed on paper, tablets, or computers, participants are encouraged to fill out the surveys independently, with support staff available to assist only with technical or procedural difficulties. These staff members, including volunteers, organizers, and educators, are trained to explain the purpose of the survey and to facilitate the process while refraining from influencing responses.

For activities conducted **in a school setting**, surveys are administered to students beginning from the 7th grade of the third cycle of basic education, which corresponds to students aged 12 years and older.

The primary aim of the surveys is to gather statistical insights about the audience, assess their engagement with science both in and outside educational contexts, and evaluate their satisfaction with the event.

Furthermore, the project follows the **evaluation methodology previously applied in the Horizon 2020 project REGGAE (Researchers for European Green Growth Education)**, which was proposed, managed, and implemented by the same consortium leading EU-EMBRACES. The full data collection protocol was submitted to and approved by the **i3S ethics committee**, ensuring compliance with rigorous ethical standards.

This approach ensures that the project's impact assessment is both ethically sound and aligned with the values and requirements of Horizon-funded initiatives, promoting transparency and respect for all participants involved.

4. | Summary of the activities assessed

4.1 Science takes the Streets: build-up activities

Build-up events were activities organised in the lead-up to the ERN for each of the two editions, designed to raise awareness of the upcoming main events and to build momentum and anticipation. Consequently, these events were held in a wide variety of locations, including streets, markets, squares, natural parks, gardens, museums, theatres, beaches, schools, associations, and numerous other venues across cities and villages in the country. Their purpose, similar to that of the ERN, was to bring researchers closer to the public, often with the specific feature of reaching people where they were, rather than relying on them to attend specific venues. This approach proved particularly valuable for engaging individuals who typically do not participate in science communication activities, and groups at risk of social exclusion, such as minorities, migrants.

The impact assessment for each build-up event was based on an **online activity report** completed by the partner responsible for organizing the event, along with a survey directed at the participating researchers.

The online report collected information describing the activity, characterising the participants and their context, and summarising the activity's perceived impact on participants, as well as details regarding the researchers involved.

The **survey for researchers** gathered information about their profile, their usual involvement in science communication activities, their impressions of the audience, their satisfaction with their participation, and the positive aspects and challenges they experienced.

The full set of questions for both tools is provided in the appendix.

4.2 European Researchers' Night (ERN)

The ERN was the flagship event of the project, taking place across nine venues throughout the country for each of the two editions. Over the course of three to 13 hours, attendees had the opportunity to engage with, learn about, and experience firsthand the research being carried out in Portugal. They interacted with research institutions, companies, NGOs, associations, school science clubs, as well as with the scientists, experts, and students who contribute to the scientific landscape. The event also provided an opportunity to increase public familiarity with the EU's five Missions and with European research projects conducted in Portugal.

A wide range of activities was offered, including demonstrations, hands-on experiments, talks, speed-dating with researchers, guided tours, games, performances, exhibitions, and various other formats designed to appeal to diverse audiences.

The evaluation of the ERN events was the most comprehensive and incorporated tools tailored to participants, researchers, and the organising partners.

Attendees were invited to complete a **survey** designed to characterise the ERN audience and capture their perceptions of the event. This survey assessed the public's profile, satisfaction, and perceived impact of the activities. In addition, dynamic and interactive methods were used to gather insights into participants' views on science and technology and the EU Missions. These included voting walls, where participants responded to questions by placing stickers (**dot-mocracy**) or writing their answers on post-it notes (**post-it walls**).

Researchers' perceptions were assessed using a **survey** similar to the one employed for the build-up events. It collected information on their profile, their typical involvement in science communication activities, their impressions of the audience, their satisfaction with their participation, and the positive aspects and challenges they encountered.

The **organising partners** submitted an online **activity report** describing the activities they hosted. This report included detailed information about the event, participant demographics and contexts, an evaluation of the activities' perceived impact on participants, and information about the researchers involved.

The full set of evaluation questions is provided in the appendix.

4.3 Meet the Scientists program

The Meet the Scientists Program organised interactive sessions, both **in schools** and **online**, bringing together researchers and students aged 6 to 17. These events aimed to spark curiosity and foster a connection between young audiences and the world of science through hands-on experiments, workshops, oral presentations, discussions about research fields and careers, and exploration of how science can be applied in daily life. The programme had a dual purpose: on one hand, to inspire young people – including those from underserved or minority backgrounds– to consider pursuing scientific careers; and on the other hand, to provide researchers with an opportunity to engage directly with young audiences, share their research outcomes, and enhance their science communication skills.

The evaluation of the Meet the Scientists Programme was carried out through activity reports and surveys.

Teachers, who attended the sessions as observers, completed an online activity report providing an external perspective on the activity. The report included fields to describe the activity and its alignment with EU Missions (if applicable), characterise the participating students and the school context, and detail the researchers involved. It also focused on the interaction between students and researchers and assessed the activity's impact on the students. Teachers could attach photographs to the report, provided they had obtained the necessary permissions and ensured that no students' faces were visible (e.g., photos taken from behind) and that no student was identifiable.

Students aged 12 and above were invited to complete a survey that gathered their profiles, satisfaction levels, and perceptions of the activity's impact. The survey also explored their prior experience with researchers and science, providing valuable insights into the extent to which the programme succeeded in reaching new audiences and how it shaped their perceptions of, and interest in, science.

Researchers' experiences were assessed through a survey that collected information about their professional profiles, typical engagement in science communication activities, impressions of the students, satisfaction with their participation, and reflections on the positive aspects and challenges they encountered during the events.

The full set of evaluation questions is provided in the appendix.

4.5 Participatory debates

Participatory debates were in-person events designed for students aged 12 to 17, aimed at **raising awareness of the EU Missions** and the research carried out in Portugal in connection with them. By engaging with cutting-edge scientific and societal topics, and supported by researchers, experts, and science mediators, students were encouraged to **develop critical thinking and debate skills**. These dialogue-based activities helped participants gain a deeper understanding of the relevance of the EU Missions and their potential in addressing major societal challenges.

The impact assessment of the participatory debates was carried out using a combination of tools: an online activity report completed by the organizing partners, as well as surveys targeted at students and researchers.

The **online activity report** documented each event and its alignment with the EU Missions, characterized the participating students, and recorded any efforts made to reach diverse audiences and promote inclusivity. It also provided information on the researchers involved and included an evaluation of the activity's perceived impact on the students.

Students were invited to complete a survey capturing their profiles, satisfaction with the event, previous experiences with researchers and science, and their perception of the event's impact. A key question asks whether they felt their opinions were valued in shaping the conclusions of the debate.

Researchers completed a separate survey assessing their professional backgrounds, prior involvement in science communication, impressions of the participating students, satisfaction with their role in the debates, and reflections on the positive aspects and challenges encountered during the activity.

The full set of evaluation questions is provided in the appendix.

4.5 Social Inclusion through Science and Technology

The **Social Inclusion through Science and Technology** programme comprised a set of outreach activities designed to promote engagement with scientists and increase awareness of research, science, and technology among communities with limited access to such opportunities. These events were implemented in underserved neighbourhoods and schools, aiming to democratize access to scientific knowledge, stimulate curiosity, and encourage active citizenship.

The programme primarily targeted communities in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts and reached diverse demographic groups, including children, families, seniors, and migrant populations. Activities were organised in two main formats:

1. **Activities and Workshops in Underserved Neighbourhoods** – Open sessions designed for all age groups, offering informal and accessible learning experiences within the community.
2. **Activities and Workshops in TEIP Schools** – Sessions specifically tailored for students aged 6–17 attending TEIP schools (Territórios Educativos de Intervenção Prioritária). These schools are located in socio-culturally disadvantaged areas and operate under a national programme of the Portuguese Ministry of Education that aims to reduce early school dropout, improve academic attainment, and promote social inclusion through strategies adapted to each community's needs.

For each type of event we used customized evaluation tools to measure its impact, as outlined below.

Activities and Workshops in Underserved Neighborhoods

Each activity was documented through an **online activity report** completed by the **organising partners**. This report described the activity, characterised the participants and their contextual background, and assessed the involvement of local organisations or community members. When such local support was present,

organisers evaluated its relevance to the successful implementation and reception of the activity. The report also provided an overview of the event's impact on participants and included information about the participating scientists, including whether their recruitment posed particular challenges compared with other outreach initiatives.

Whenever feasible, **participants** were invited to provide feedback. **Surveys** were used to collect information on participant profiles, levels of satisfaction, and perceptions of the activity's relevance and impact. In situations where written surveys were impractical, **alternative methods** were employed –such as observation or simple show-of-hands polls– allowing participants to express their views on satisfaction, perceived impact, and their relationship with science in an accessible and engaging manner.

Researchers' experiences were assessed through **online surveys**. These questionnaires collected information on their professional background, prior experience in science communication, and their impressions of the activity. Scientists were asked to reflect on their satisfaction with the experience, the positive elements of their participation, and any challenges or areas where improvements could be made.

Activities and Workshops in TEIP Schools

The activities carried out in TEIP schools were evaluated using the same methodology applied in the *Meet the Scientist* campaign, ensuring coherence across the assessment framework.

Teachers, who attended the sessions as observers, completed an online **activity report** providing an external perspective on each activity. These reports described the activity, noted its alignment with the EU Missions where relevant, and characterised the participating students and school context. Teachers also documented the interaction between students and researchers, assessed the activity's impact, and provided information about the researchers involved. Teachers could also submit photographs, provided they had obtained the necessary permissions and ensured student anonymity by avoiding identifiable images (e.g., photos taken from behind).

Students aged 12 and above were invited to complete an online **survey** capturing their profiles, satisfaction with the activity, and perceived impact. The survey also gathered information about students' previous contact with scientists and science, offering insights into how the sessions influenced their perceptions, interest, and sense of connection with research.

Researchers participating in the TEIP school activities were likewise **surveyed**. Their responses provided information on professional background and prior experience in science communication, as well as their impressions of the students and the overall activity. Researchers were asked to reflect on positive aspects of the initiative, challenges encountered, and suggestions for improvement.

The full set of evaluation questions is provided in the appendix.

4.6 | Youth Embassadors Program

The **Youth Ambassador Program** mobilized a network of students engaged in science clubs to take an active role in the ERNs. These students participated alongside researchers, presenting their own projects and showcasing the work developed within their clubs. The initiative aimed to strengthen students' communication skills, empower them as science ambassadors within their communities, and enhance their participation in the ERN activities.

To prepare them for this role, partners organized a hands-on and interactive **science communication workshop**. In this training session, students learned practical principles of effective science communication, both for in-person interactions and digital formats. The workshop supported them in crafting the pitch for the project they would present during the ERN and introduced additional challenges related to the creation of content for the official ERN social media channels.

Organizers completed an **online activity report** that included detailed information about the event, participant demographics and contexts, the facilitators involved, and an evaluation of the activities' perceived impact on participants.

5. | Findings and Results

5.1 Build-up activities and European Researchers Night

Build-up events

Across both editions, the build-up events offered a wide range of immersive and participatory science experiences, bringing research and researchers into everyday public spaces and contexts.

In 2025, activities included, for example, beach walks combining seawater quality testing with microscopic observation of marine microorganisms; visits to research centres featuring scientific escape rooms, laboratory experiments, and direct dialogue with researchers; Science Cafés in innovation hubs exploring the role of

robotics in sustainable agriculture, textile recycling, and electronic waste management; museum workshops addressing topics such as intangible heritage, gender archaeology, and the social impacts of technology; and field activities focused on biodiversity monitoring, including nocturnal observations of butterflies and lichens using digital identification tools. Other events involved sustainable cooking with edible algae, pedal-powered simulations of renewable energy generation in public squares, and interactive sessions in schools and health centres on topics ranging from underwater archaeology to cancer research.

In 2024, build-up events similarly combined scientific content with informal and culturally embedded settings. Examples included discussions on fermentation and citizen science while tasting hydromel on the beach; interactive installations using bicycles to demonstrate clean energy production; guided walks in natural parks to explore soil formation processes; visits to regenerative agriculture farms; science activities in cruise terminals focused on aquatic environments; storytelling and origami workshops in public markets; and school-based photography exhibitions addressing cancer therapies and social stigma.

One of the most significant strengths of the build-up programme in both editions was its ability to take science beyond traditional institutional settings. By activating streets, squares, public markets, beaches, theatres, natural parks, municipal buildings, museums, cafés, and innovation centres, the events lowered barriers to participation and facilitated encounters with audiences who might not typically attend formal science events.

Across both editions, the programme included **63 build-up events** (32 in 2024 and 31 in 2025) held in a wide range of contexts: research institutes, science centres, and universities, but also beaches, museums, schools, hospitals and health centres, markets, natural parks, monasteries, wetlands, urban public spaces, cultural centres, cafés and restaurants, innovation hubs, and outdoor field sites.

These events offered hands-on workshops, science cafés, guided tours, field excursions, microscopy and observation sessions, escape rooms, interactive exhibitions, quizzes, debates, open days, storytelling and reading sessions, awareness-raising activities, demonstrations, participatory murals, and practical

science-communication exercises. They covered topics spanning microbiology, chemistry, robotics and technology, bioindicators and biodiversity, ecology and conservation, archaeology (including gender and underwater archaeology), geology, environmental sciences, cardiovascular and cancer research, renewable energy, road safety, nutrition and marine resources, intangible heritage, and science communication.

The events collectively involved **39,363 participants** (27,427 in 2024; 11,936 in 2025) and **616 researchers** (284 in 2024; 332 in 2025) (Figure 1). Among them, **3** events were specifically designed for underserved audiences—including migrant communities, at-risk youth, and socially and economically vulnerable groups—while **10** events targeted students. The remaining events reached families, seniors, teachers, and the general public.

Given the diverse nature of the events, most of the **feedback and comments from participants** came from observations made by the organizers or from transcriptions of remarks during conversations and exchanges of opinions stimulated by the events. Across the build-up events, in both years, participants reported significant shifts in knowledge, attitudes, and awareness, ranging from discovering ecological diversity (e.g., lichens, macroinvertebrates, bats, nocturnal insects) to correcting *Figure 1. Geographical distribution of build-up events in 2024 (pink) and 2025 (violet) across*

continental Portugal; number of participants (left) and researchers (right) involved in each event.

Source of data: activity reports from organizing partners.

misconceptions and recognizing the scientific value of familiar places. Many

Participants in Build-up events 2024/25

Source: reports from organizing partners • Created with Datawrapper

Researchers in Build-up events 2024/25

Source: reports from organizing partners • Created with Datawrapper

experienced first-time encounters with researchers, scientific tools, museums, or field. In events from 2024 editions, where surveys were administered, 14% of respondents reported that they had never attended a science event, and 25% claimed they had no connection to science.

In the case of lectures, exhibitions, or walks, many reported comments referred to the level of public engagement.

The events held between May and September, in 2024, and between March and September, in 2025, served as valuable opportunities to raise awareness, although not quantifiable, while also inviting participation in the main **Night Event** of September.

ERN

In each edition, the EU-EMBRACES project organized **9 ERNs** in **diverse locations**, such as the Oeiras seafront, the i3S research center on the outskirts of Porto, the *Pavilhão do Conhecimento* exhibition center in Lisbon, the planetarium at the Monastery of Tibães (Braga), an old hydroelectric power station located on the left bank of the Fervença River, now home to the Bragança Ciência Viva Center, the museum near the archaeological site of rock art in the Côa and Douro Valleys (Vila Nova de Foz Côa), the Alviela Ciência Viva Center near Portugal's largest karst spring, the Convento das Maltezas which houses the Estremoz Ciência Viva Center, and the Ciência Viva Center of Lagos located in the heart of the city.

These events, attended by anywhere from around 50 to more than 2,000 participants, totaled more than **10,000 attendees** (4,918 in 2024 and 5,800 in 2025) during the afternoon and evening of the last Friday of September, along with more than **800 researchers** (511 in 2024 and 809 in 2025) (Figure 2 and Figure 5).

On average, events lasted around **six hours**, with durations at individual venues ranging from approximately three to thirteen hours.

Each edition of the ERN hosted over **200 activities**, a rich and diverse programme that combined hands-on science, interactive exhibits, performances, and thematic activities tailored to different audiences. Visitors engaged with researchers through experiments, games, quizzes, demonstrations, tasting sessions, debates, guided tours, workshops, planetarium shows, informal conversations, and artistic installations. Fields and topics covered spanned a wide scientific spectrum: from ageing, food science, molecular gastronomy, ecology, biodiversity, wetlands, soil and water contamination, rock-art conservation, climate change, and sustainable agriculture, to artificial intelligence, personalised medicine, oncology, quantum physics, astronomy, geology, palaeontology, and all the five EU Missions.

Activities ranged from large fairs (outdoor or indoor) with dozens of scientific booths and stage programmes (Oeiras, Porto, Lisbon, Bragança) to more focused thematic days or thematic evenings dedicated to topics such as cancer research (Alviela, Lagos), wetland ecology and biodiversity conservation (Braga), soil and water contamination and rock-art conservation (Côa), and exhibitions and activities linking geology, palaeontology and the Anthropocene (Estremoz).

Figure 2. Geographical distribution of ERNs in 2024 (pink) and 2025 (violet): number of participants per event (left), and postal codes of participants for each venue (right).

Source of data: activity reports from organizing partners (left); ERN participant surveys (n=2,169)

Participants could observe insects, explore ecosystems on guided walks, experiment with scientific tools, taste innovative foods (including insect-based products), solve escape rooms, enjoy magic-and-science shows, get to know citizen-science initiatives, and meet researchers in relaxed formats such as Pint of Science and speed-dating sessions.

EU Corners in Bragança, Lagos, Lisbon, Oeiras, and Porto, highlighted EU-funded research in Portugal and related opportunities. Across both editions, in Oeiras venue, special efforts were made to **engage communities with limited access to science communication**, including musicians and dancers from underserved neighbourhoods, the deaf community (with guided visits and on-stage activities

translated into Portuguese Sign Language through the collaboration of sign-language interpreters), individuals facing social and economic challenges such

Figure 3. Demographics of ERN participants in 2024 (grey) and 2025 (violet): age distribution (top left), gender distribution (bottom left), education level (BE = Basic Education; SE = Superior Education) (top right), and employment status (bottom right).

Source of data: participant surveys (n = 971 in 2024; n = 1198 in 2025).

as deprivation, exclusion, and risk, as well as vocational high-school students specialising in communication.

Through the collection of **participant surveys (971 in 2024 and 1,198 in 2025)**, distributed in paper format or online, based on the needs and characteristics of each venue, we gained valuable insights into our audience. The majority of attendees were young, with **40% under the age of 25**, while **6% were over 65**. Additionally, nearly 90% were evenly split between students and employed individuals, and 60% of respondents identified as female (Figure 3).

One of the most striking findings was that nearly **20%** of participants were

encountering a scientist for the first time (Figure 4). In addition, about **25%** reported having **no prior connection to science**. Among these **newcomers**, approximately half were under 25 years old (50% in 2024 and 40% in 2025). Beyond this age group, participation was more evenly distributed across age ranges; in 2025, a notable increase was observed among participants aged 45–54, who represented 19% of respondents. Overall, these results indicate that the event successfully engaged a **broad and diverse demographic**.

Among participants, 61% in 2024 and 55% in 2025 had completed post-secondary education. Considering that, in 2024, tertiary educational attainment in Portugal stood at 43%—where tertiary attainment refers to the share of the population that has completed post-secondary education, including universities, colleges, and vocational schools, and earned certificates, diplomas, or degrees—these results suggest that the audience of the European Researchers’ Night is, on average, more highly educated than the general population.

When asked to rate their overall **satisfaction** on a scale from 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied), over **90% gave a positive evaluation** (4 or 5), with 70% selecting the highest rating of 5. This demonstrates an overwhelmingly positive reception (Figure 4).

We also asked participants what they appreciated most and what could be improved. The most successful activities in 2025 included:

1. Hands-on and Experimental Activities

- **Laboratory and scientific experiments:** Microscopy and observation of zooplankton, blood, corals, insects; DNA extraction; chemistry demonstrations such as elephant toothpaste, coconut foam, and sunscreen formulation.
- **Robotics and engineering:** Human gyroscope, robot demonstrations, welding activities, drones, electronic circuits, and smart-fibre technologies.
- **Scientific cooking and sustainability:** Preparation and tasting of seaweed rice, molecular gastronomy demonstrations, honey tasting, hydroponics, Mediterranean diet exploration, and edible-insect sampling.
- **Sensorial science:** Olive-oil analysis, aroma identification, and tasting-based learning experiences.
- **Scientific crafts and maker workshops:** DNA-bracelet creation, rocket building, and experiments with non-Newtonian fluids.

2. Informal Talks and Q&A with Researchers

- **Science cafés and slow dating events:** Informal exchanges on topics such as cancer research, environmental challenges, biomedical innovation, and scientific careers.
- **Thematic discussions:** Advances in cancer therapies, climate change, healthy eating, sustainability, and health innovation.
- **Sharing scientific journeys:** Researchers discussed their personal and professional paths, fostering curiosity and approachable dialogue.

3. Quizzes and Interactive Games

- **"What Is This?"** – identification games using scientific objects or concepts.
- **"Who Wants to Be a Scientist?"** – a quiz inspired by *Who Wants to Be a Millionaire?*, focused on science knowledge.
- **Aroma challenges and sensory riddles:** Guessing flavours and smells while learning about sensorial science.
- **Health and biomedicine quizzes:** Interactive questions testing public knowledge in these domains.

Analogously, In 2024, the most appreciated activities included:

- **Interactive Experiences:** Human gyroscope, suspended bicycle, and hands-on activities in plant biology and microbiology
- **Workshops:** Coral conservation, nutrition, and sustainable agriculture
- **Exhibitions:** Cancer research and microbiology
- **Science Shows:** with live chemistry experiments
- **Demonstrations:** Food technology, lab-grown food, robotics, hydrogen and electric cars, autonomous FI cars, hydroponics, biomaterials, and artificial organs
- **Informal Talks:** Climate change from historical, geological, and contemporary perspectives
- **Games & Virtual Tours:** Escape room game on epidemics and research methods, antibiotic resistance, virtual guided tours undersea conservation, cosmic rays, and boat tours.

Figure 4. Public's Connection with Science and Satisfaction Levels in ERN 2024 (grey) and 2025 (violet): Percentage of attendees who had their first contact with researchers during the event (top left), age distribution of those experiencing their first interaction with a scientist (bottom left), attendees' connection to science (categories: No direct connection to science, Friends or family work in science, Trained in a scientific field, Work or have worked in science, Other) (top right) and satisfaction levels of attendees from 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied) (bottom right).

Source of data: participant surveys ($n = 971$ in 2024; $n = 1198$ in 2025).

Across both the 2024 and 2025 editions, participants consistently praised the **diversity of activities and scientific themes**, highlighting the opportunity to explore a wide spectrum of research areas in a single event. Visitors in both years particularly valued the **direct interaction with researchers**, frequently mentioning the clarity of explanations, the scientists' enthusiasm and friendliness, and the informal atmosphere that made learning accessible and engaging. The **hands-on nature of many activities** was repeatedly cited as one of the greatest strengths of the event, helping transform abstract scientific concepts into tangible and memorable experiences. The overall **welcoming and vibrant atmosphere** also stood out across editions, with many noting the strong presence of young people—as visitors, organizers, and presenters—which contributed to a dynamic, intergenerational environment.

Some specific elements emerged year by year. In 2024, participants particularly highlighted the **involvement of multiple institutions and research centres**, as well as

the **tailored sessions for different age groups**, from children to adults. The diversity of the audience—students, families, teachers—was also frequently mentioned. In 2025, attendees more often commented on the **smooth organization**, noting that the event felt well coordinated and easy to navigate. They also emphasized the value of the **open and intimate exchanges** offered through science cafés, slow-dating formats, and thematic discussions.

Figure 5. Researchers Participating in ERN 2024 (grey) and 2025 (yellow): Frequency of researchers' participation in science communication activities with direct public engagement (left) and geographical distribution of participation, showing the number of researchers involved across the 9 venues (right).

Data Source: Researchers online surveys ($n=102$ in 2024, $n=164$ in 2025) (left); Reports from organizing partners (right)

Regarding areas for improvement, both editions revealed similar challenges. The most common suggestions across years concerned **limited space due to high attendance**, and a shared desire for a **longer or multi-day event** to allow visitors to explore more activities without feeling rushed. Calls for **greater outreach and promotion** were also present in both editions, although in 2024 several participants pointed out that the high turnout suggested a need for larger venues rather than increased publicity. In smaller locations in 2024, some attendees expressed a wish for more activity variety—

highlighting strong public interest even when resources limited the number of offerings.

Taken together, the **feedback** from both editions demonstrates remarkable **consistency**: the European Researchers' Night is **widely appreciated** for its **inclusiveness, interactivity, and scientific richness**, while **logistical constraints** linked to its growing popularity remain the primary area to address in future editions.

Figure 6 presents participants' preferences regarding increased financing for the EU Missions, based on data collected during the European Researchers' Nights (ERNs) using Dotmocracy voting systems. Overall, **50% of the votes** were concentrated on two missions: the **Climate Change Adaptation Mission** ("Supporting at least 150 communities by 2030 in understanding climate risks, developing preparedness pathways, and implementing innovative solutions") and the **Cancer Mission** ("Improving the lives of more than 3 million people by 2030 through prevention, cure, and enabling those affected by cancer, including their families, to live longer and better lives"). These were followed by the **Restore Our Ocean and Waters Mission** (22%), the **Soil Deal for Europe / Food Systems Mission** (21%), and the **Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Mission** (8%).

When comparing preferences across different territories, notable variations emerge that appear to be linked to local contexts. For instance, **Lagos**, a coastal city in the Algarve with a strong fishing and maritime tradition, showed a clear preference for the **Restore Our Ocean and Waters Mission**, reflecting the region's close connection to marine environments and ocean conservation challenges. In contrast, **Lisbon**, as the capital and largest metropolitan area in Portugal, registered a significantly higher share of votes for the **Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Mission**, likely influenced by its urban scale and the concentration of technological, environmental, and sustainability initiatives that shape public engagement with urban innovation.

WHICH EUROPEAN UNION MISSION SHOULD RECIEVE MORE FINANCING?

WHICH EUROPEAN UNION MISSION SHOULD RECIEVE MORE FINANCING?

Figure 6. Distribution of participants' preferences for EU Missions to receive increasing financing, based on the Dotmocracy results collected during the European Researchers' Night, in all venues (top) and across four representative venues (Lisbon, Oeiras, Bragança, and Lagos).

Data source: activity reports from organizing partners (Lisbon, Oeiras, Bragança, and Lagos).

In each edition, around **800 researchers** participated in the build-up events and European Researchers' Night (ERN). To assess their experience and impact, we collected online survey responses, representing approximately **20%** of all participating researchers. In 2024, **284 researchers** took part in build-up events (with **53 survey responses**) and **511** participated in the ERN (with **102 responses**). In 2025, **332 researchers** were involved in build-up events (**69 responses**) and **809** participated in the ERN (**164 responses**). Altogether, we collected **388 completed surveys**. The data provides valuable insights into the demographics and engagement patterns of participating scientists.

Among the surveyed researchers, **13%** were **participating in a public science communication event** with direct audience engagement **for the first time** (compared with 10% in 2024), while **14%** reported frequent participation, taking part in more than five outreach events per year (23% in 2024) (Figure 5).

These findings indicate a **growing engagement of researchers in the ERN** and suggest that large, community-oriented events such as the build-up activities and the **ERN itself encourage first-time participation in science communication**.

High frequency of respondents (37% in 2024 and 42% in 2025) were **under 35 years old**, reflecting a trend also observed in the participant surveys. However, researchers from all age groups took part, including 5% aged over 65 in 2024 that decreased to 1% in 2025 (Figure 6).

In terms of professional category, the most two represented groups were career researchers or lecturers (29% in 2024 and 32% in 2025), and PhD researchers with a scholarship or fixed-term contract (30% in 2024 and 25% in 2025), followed by PhD students (19% in 2024 and 18% in 2025). Finally, 62% of respondents in 2024 and 77% in 2025 identified as female. According to the Elsevier report *Gender in the Portugal Research Arena: A Case Study in European Leadership* (2021), women represent approximately 48% of researchers in Portugal. This overrepresentation suggests a particularly strong participation of women researchers in ERN. However, it may also partly reflect a higher propensity among women to respond to surveys, a pattern that has been already documented in the literature on survey participation and gender differences.

The participating researchers came from diverse scientific disciplines, including biological sciences, physical sciences, exact sciences, social sciences, engineering, medicine, law, and humanities. However, the majority (49% in 2024 and 66% in 2025)

were from the natural sciences, highlighting a strong presence of researchers in these fields.

Figure 7. Demographic of researchers that participated in build-up and ERN activities in 2024 (grey) and 2025 (yellow): age distribution (top left), gender distribution (bottom left), professional career distribution (top right) and research area (bottom right).

Data Source: researchers online surveys (102 = in 2024 and 164 = in 2025)

5.2 Researchers at Schools Activities

Researchers at schools activities includes the *Meet the Scientists* program, the *Participatory Debates*, the *Social Inclusion through Science and Technology* program and the *Youth Ambassadors* program.

Across 2024 and 2025, a total of **158 Meet the Scientists sessions** took place, engaging **6,052 students** aged 6 to 18 (Figure 9) and involving **184 scientists**. Of these, 74 sessions were held in person, while the remaining sessions were conducted online; together, they reached schools distributed across the entire country (Figure 8). Among the participating students, 4,546 were over 12 years old and therefore eligible to respond to the surveys. We collected **survey data** from 1,808 students, corresponding to **40% of those eligible**. In addition, we gathered evaluation data

PARTICIPANTS IN RESEARCHERS AT SCHOOLS 2024/25

Figure 8: Geographical distribution and number of participants for each event of Researchers at School in 2024 and 2025: Meet the Scientist (left), Social Inclusion through Science (middle), Participatory debates (right). Source of data: activity reports from organizing partners, n=158 (left), n=39 (middle), n=18 (right).

STUDENTS' DISTRIBUTION BY GRADE

MOTHER'S EDUCATION LEVEL

Figure 9: Distribution of students participating in Meet the Scientist campaign, by grade level (left) and mother's education level (right). Data Source: activity reports from organizing partner (158 sessions; 6,052 participating students).

from 82 participating researchers, representing **45% of the total**.

Among the participants, approximately half of the students were in secondary school and half in primary school, and 47% of students’ mothers had completed higher education.

The vast majority of students reported high levels of satisfaction with the activities, with 47% rating them as 5, 43% as 4, and 9% as 3 on the evaluation scale.

Observations indicate that the proportion of students who had direct contact with a scientist for the first time was higher than among participants in the ERN reaching 29%, with an additional 13% of students unsure whether it was their first such experience and (Figure 10 and Figure 12). and 43% of them have never participated in science related activities outside school (Figure 10).

Figure : Students’ Connection with Science and Satisfaction Levels in Meet the Scientist campaign. Percentage of students who had their first contact with researchers during the events (top left), percentage of students who had participated in science activities outside school (top left), percentage of students that think they could become a scientist (top right), and satisfaction levels of attendees from 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied) (bottom right)

Source of data: students surveys (n = 1,808).

Figure 11: Demographic of researchers that participated in Researchers at Schools activities in 2024 and 2025: age distribution (top left), gender distribution (bottom left), professional career distribution (top right) and research area (bottom right).

Data Source: researchers online surveys (n= 131)

Regarding the **researchers** involved in school activities, we observed that **all of them had prior experience in direct public engagement**. This result suggest that while the ERN and its build-up events serve as an entry point for researchers new to outreach activities, those who engage in school-based initiatives tend to already have prior experience in science communication activities.

Also in this case, as observed for the ERN, we note a higher proportion of female researchers compared to the national Portuguese research demographics. This suggests that women researchers may be more inclined than their male counterparts to participate in outreach and public engagement activities.

Additionally, **39** activities focused on **social inclusion through science** were organized: **35** in disadvantaged neighborhoods, in collaboration with associations working with groups at risk of social exclusion due to unemployment, as well as in juvenile detention centers. These activities engaged **615** participants, involving diverse audiences,

including older adults, and **47** scientists, with the aim of democratizing access to scientific knowledge and fostering active citizenship.

In most cases, organizers highlighted the importance of connections with local associations or of building on previous collaborative activities, which proved essential for effective engagement.

In addition, **4** activities were conducted in **TEIP** schools –schools with historically high dropout rates and retention challenges- involving **70** students and **11** scientists.

A total of **38** participant questionnaires were collected for activities held in disadvantaged neighborhoods, corresponding to approximately **6%** of participants. This relatively low response rate reflects the fact that, in several cases, the target audiences faced greater difficulties in completing written surveys. In contrast, around **70%** of students participating in school-based activities responded to the questionnaires.

WAS THIS THE FIRST TIME YOU HAD CONTACT WITH A SCIENTIST?

Figure 12: Connection with Science for participants in ERNs (2024 and 2025), Meet the Scientist Campaign and Social inclusion through Science.

Source of data: participant surveys (n=2,169 for ERNs, n=6,052 for Meet the Scientists, n= 86 for Social Inclusion events).

In social inclusion activities, the proportion of participants who stated that this was their first contact with a scientist was **33%** –the highest across all activity types– while an additional **7%** reported being unsure.

Additionally, **39 activities** di inclusione sociale attraverso la scienza were organized: 35 in disadvantaged neighborhoods, in associazioni che lavorano con groups at risk of social exclusion in seguito a perdita di lavoro, in centri di detenzione per minori, engaging **615 participants**, coinvolgendo pubblici vari inclusi elderly, and **47 scientists**, with the goal of democratizing access to scientific knowledge and fostering active citizenship. Nella maggiorparte dei casi gli organizzatori hanno riferito come importante la connessione con qualche associazione del territorio o precedenti attività svolte insieme.

Finally, the project also organized **18 participatory debates** involving **379 students** aged 12 to 17 (**Figure 8**) and more than **40 scientists**, each debates with 1 to 4 scientists.

The Youth Ambassador Programme successfully engaged students from science clubs and schools in active roles during the European Researchers' Night (ERN).

In 2024, 154 students from 9 science clubs led and facilitated activities during the ERN of Lisbon, while in 2025, 268 students led stands in Lisbon, Porto, and Oeiras ERNs.

In 2025 four scicomm workshop in scicomm were organized, involving 106 students preparing them to present their projects and communicate effectively alongside researchers. Workshops, focused on practical science communication skills, including pitching, storytelling, audience adaptation, and creating content for social media. Across all sessions, students were attentive, enthusiastic, and highly participative.

Organizers observed tangible improvements in students' confidence, public speaking, creativity, and ability to synthesize information. Students produced high-quality outputs, such as videos and presentations, demonstrating autonomy, proactivity, and teamwork. During the ERNs, these Youth Ambassadors successfully engaged diverse audiences, attracting attention to their stands and contributing to the overall success of the events.

Overall, the programme empowered students as science communicators within their communities, strengthened their role in public engagement, and enhanced the inclusiveness and impact of the ERNs. The results highlight the importance of sustained communication training to further consolidate these skills and foster lasting curiosity and participation in science among young people.

5.3 Dissemination and communication activities

The impact evaluation of the ERN project extends beyond the events themselves and beyond the perspectives and impressions of the participants, including the public, researchers, and event organizers. Specifically, the impact also includes the dissemination of the project and the ERN, along with the related events. Communication and dissemination activities have proven to be a fundamental aspect of the project's overall impact, demonstrating the ability to generate interest and participation from a wide range of audiences.

As detailed in **Deliverable D1.2 – Awareness Campaign 2024** and **Deliverable D6.1 – Awareness Campaign 2025**, the ERN project achieved extensive media coverage across both editions, with visibility on more than **37 major media platforms**, including leading television channels and online news outlets. Key media included *Público*, a national digital newspaper with over **54,000 paid subscribers**, *CMTV*, a television channel with a daily audience exceeding **100,000 viewers** and a **6.2% total audience share in September 2025**, and *SIC*, which reached a **14.6% audience share** in the same period.

In both editions, a promotional ERN video was broadcast on **RTP2** and **RTP3**—channels of Rádio e Televisão de Portugal that together account for approximately **1.7% of the national audience share**—as well as on **Antena 1**, one of RTP's national public radio channels.

In addition, a digital advertising campaign in *Público* generated more than **127,000 impressions**, significantly enhancing the visibility of the ERN and its associated activities.

The project's digital outreach further reinforced its impact, reaching approximately **103,000 social media users**, while the ERN website attracted **18,700 unique visitors**, demonstrating strong online engagement and interest in the project.

6. | Challenge and limitations

6.1 Challenges in data collection and analysis

One of the main challenges in data collection was ensuring **standardization across the diverse venues** involved in the consortium. These venues range from research institutes to science centres and museums, with varying levels of resources and operating in very different territorial and social contexts. Consequently, the events themselves differed widely in format, scale, and setting, taking place in large cities, suburban areas, smaller urban centres, and, in some cases, outside urban environments altogether. This diversity made it difficult to apply uniform data collection methods and to ensure full comparability of results across venues.

Another significant challenge concerned achieving **high response rates from participants**, particularly in large-scale events and activities held in open public spaces. In contrast, data collection in school-based activities proved to be more straightforward and consistently effective. To mitigate low response rates at public events, **paper surveys** were distributed (instead of online ones) at venues where this was feasible. While this approach helped increase participation, it also generated **additional costs and workload**, as paper responses had to be digitised before being integrated into the central data analysis.

Some venues experimented with **small incentives** to encourage survey completion. Examples included ERN-branded tote bags with science-related wordplay (Oeiras), ERN-logo pencils (Alviela, Bragança, Lagos, Porto), and ERN-branded anti-stress balls (Lisbon). Although the use of incentives was not always possible due to budgetary constraints, this strategy proved **effective** in increasing response rates. Conversely, venues that relied exclusively on online surveys and were unable to offer any incentive generally recorded lower participation levels.

Securing survey **responses from researchers** constituted a further challenge, particularly in large-scale events such as the European Researchers' Night. In these contexts, participating researchers were often affiliated with multiple institutions, meaning that communication between event organizers and individual researchers was not always direct. This may have reduced researchers' engagement with post-event evaluation activities. We observed, however, that inviting researchers to **complete the survey on-site**, during the event itself, significantly increased response rates compared to follow-up requests sent after the event.

6.2 Limitations of the assessment tools and methodology

While our impact evaluation provides valuable insights, it is important to recognize the limitations inherent in the assessment tools employed, such as surveys, reports, and voting walls. These tools primarily capture immediate impacts, but they are less effective at measuring long-term outcomes. First and foremost, it is important to note, as previously mentioned, that the realization of the events themselves represents an impact in its own right, even if its full effects are not immediately measurable. Regarding long-term outcomes, the gradual familiarization of the public with the ERN initiative, as well as the more subtle effects of public-facing materials like street posters, remain difficult to quantify. Furthermore, certain indirect impacts—such as the deeper engagement or sustained interest generated by the events—are not fully captured by our current methodologies. While the events generate immediate and measurable impact, some broader, longer-term effects may not be adequately reflected in the available data.

7. | Conclusions and Recommendations for the next editions

7.1 Summary of key results

By its conclusion, the EU-EMBRACES project successfully achieved its mission of promoting engagement and inclusivity in science communication, making substantial progress toward its key objectives and effectively reducing socio-economic barriers to access science and innovation.

The following map shows the distribution of all EU-EMBRACES activities, including public and researcher participation, illustrating the extent of the project’s reach across Portugal, including both major cities and interior areas.

Participants in EU-EMBRACES events (2024/25)

Source: reports from organizing partners; survey to teachers • Created with Datawrapper

Researchers in EU-EMBRACES events (2024/25)

Source: reports from organizing partners; surveys to teachers • Created with Datawrapper

Figure 13. Geographical distribution of EU-EMBRACES events in 2024, including Build-Up events, ERNs, and Meet the Scientists events. Participant distribution (left) and researchers involved (right).

Below is a summary of the main results for each objective followed by the project's **Impact Overview Table**, which summarises its overall progress and impact. It covers **short-term** and **mid-term** impacts and includes the following elements:

- **Foreseen Impact** – The expected outcomes for the project as a whole.
- **State of the Art Achieved** – Progress based on all collected data.
- **Additional Information** – Relevant contextual details, where applicable.

Long-term impacts—such as societal, scientific, or economic effects—are not included, as they fall outside the timeframe of this evaluation and require more time to materialise.

Table 2 - Impact overview of EU-EMBRACES

Foreseen Impact (project as a whole)	State of the art at the project concluded	Additional information (if applicable)
Short-term result		
<p>A set of activities and events involving researchers and lay-audiences, in particular young people, and underserved audiences;</p>	<p>300 activities organized (111 in 2024 and 189 in 2025)</p> <p>63 build-up events; (32 in 2024 and 31 in 2025)</p> <p>18 ERN events; (9 in each edition)</p> <p>158 meet the scientists events; (57 in 2024 and 101 in 2025)</p> <p>18 participatory debates; (1 on which in 2024)</p> <p>39 Social inclusion through science and technology events; (12 in 2024 and 27 in 2025)</p> <p>184 actions specifically with young people; (43 in 2024 and 141 in 2025)</p> <p>40% of ERN participants were under 25 years old;</p> <p>47 actions specifically with underserved audiences;</p>	<p>Counts of actions targeting young people include only those within the Researchers at School activities. Build-up and ERN activities specifically directed at young people are not included, as a complete count was not available.</p> <p>Counts of actions targeting underserved audiences include Social Inclusion through Science and Technology events, as well as 4 ERN actions in 2024 and 4 in 2025 in Oeiras aimed at underserved audiences.</p>
<p>A Youth Ambassadors network;</p>	<p>154 students from science clubs were engaged to lead and facilitate activities during the 2024 ERN.</p> <p>106 students from science clubs received training in science communication to enhance their participation and organization of</p>	

	<p>activities during the 2025 ERN, where they led stands.</p> <p>268 students led stands in 2025 ERNs.</p>	
<p>Many citizens across the country participating in science outreach activities;</p>	<p>Over 57,303 people participated in EU-Embraces science outreach events (of which 35,755 in 2024 and 21,548 in 2025)</p>	<p>Includes build-up events, the main NIGHT events, Meet the scientists campaign, Participatory debates, Social inclusion through science and technology, and Youth Ambassadors program.</p>
<p>Researchers from all scientific areas engaged in science outreach activities;</p>	<p>2,215 researchers involved (835 in 2024 and 1,380 in 2025) from research areas that includes:</p> <p>Medical and Health Sciences - 34%</p> <p>Natural Sciences - 20%</p> <p>Exact Sciences - 11%</p> <p>Engineering & Technology - 19%</p> <p>Social Sciences - 8%</p> <p>Humanities - 4%</p> <p>Education & Communication - 3%</p>	
<p>EU Missions highlighted;</p>	<p>EU missions presented in 66% of the activities;</p>	
<p>Research institutions with more visibility.</p>	<p>68 scientific institutions involved in ERN (institutional participation);</p>	
<p>Mid-term outcomes</p>		
<p>Increase the proportion of the national population engaging with science, particularly among underserved audiences such as ethnic minorities, migrants, and socio-economically</p>	<p>Among the 4,281 surveys administered to participants of outreach events, (1,569 gathered in 2024 and 2,712 in 2025)</p> <p>25% reported that this was</p>	

<p>disadvantaged populations. We anticipate that creating new opportunities for citizens to encounter science will spark greater interest in science-related issues in the future, leading to broader participation in science outreach activities and venues;</p>	<p>their first time having direct contact with a scientist.</p> <p>Focusing exclusively on surveys from participants of the <i>Meet the Scientist</i> activities (out of 1,808 surveys), this percentage increases to 29%, with an additional 13% stating that they were unsure.</p>	
<p>By involving school students in science, we expect to break barriers they may have in considering research as a potential career, showing that science is not too complicated nor uninteresting. We aim to bring a new cohort of students, specially from minorities and underserved groups, to universities, and later on to scientific and academic careers.</p>	<p>7,376 students involved (3,410 in 2024 and 3,966 in 2025)</p>	<p>This figure includes only the students who participated in the Researchers at Schools activities - including the Meet the Scientists campaign, participatory debates, Social inclusion through science and technology events, and Youth Ambassadors program.</p> <p>To this number, students who participated in the build-up events and the European Researchers' Night (ERN) should be added, although only estimates are available: approximately 760 for the 2024 build-up events, 800 for ERN 2024, and 2,000 for ERN 2025.</p>

<p>By involving researchers in different types of science outreach initiatives, we contribute to improving their communication skills and giving them new perspectives on the public's concerns and opinions on their scientific topic.</p>	<p>Number of researchers involved in outreach initiatives: 2,215 (835 in 2024 and 1,380 in 2025)</p> <p>11% of researchers known to have participated in outreach activities for the first time</p>	
<p>Research centres and universities realise the importance of participating in science outreach activities that go beyond preaching to the choir and start considering new strategies for reaching underserved audiences.</p>	<p>68 scientific institutions involved (institutional participation);</p>	<p>A number of institutions proactively reached out to the organizing partners to express their interest in participating in the ERN.</p>

Objective 1: Increase awareness of science and scientific careers.

- **300** activities organized (111 in 2024 and 189 in 2025): **63** build-up events (32 in 2024 and 31 in 2025), **18** ERN events (9 in each edition), **158** meet the scientists events (57 in 2024 and 101 in 2025), **18** participatory debates (1 on which in 2024), **39** Social inclusion through science and technology events (12 in 2024 and 27 in 2025), **4** workshops on science communication directed to Young Embassadors. **STOP**
- Participants: 57,303 attendees, 70% under 25 years old.
- *Meet the Scientists* program: 158 events, 6,052 students involved.

Objective 2: Reach new audiences and underserved communities.

- Participation: 57,303 total participants, 4,387 surveyed.
- First-time Encounters: Across all EU-EMBRACES activities, 25% of participants had their first direct contact with a scientist; 18% during the ERNs, 29% of

students in Meet the Scientists activities, and 33% in Social Inclusion through Science activities.

- Students Actions: 180 actions specifically with students, 8,000 students involved.
- Underserved Audiences: 39 activities in underserved neighborhoods/TEIP schools;
- Young audience: 40% of participants in ERNs were young.

Objective 3: Promote public engagement with science, particularly through participatory activities.

- Engagement: 154 Youth Ambassadors in 2024 and 268 in 2025, from 9 Ciência Viva clubs in 2024 and 16 in 2025; 18 participatory debates with 379 students.

Objective 4: Involve scientists in science communication activities.

- Researchers Involved: 2215 researchers from various scientific fields.
- Scientific Areas: Natural sciences (58%), Medical & Health Sciences (19%), Engineering and Technology (11%) Agricultural Sciences (12%).
- Experience: 12% of scientists had no prior public engagement experience, 51% participate in outreach regularly.

Objective 5: Showcase EU-funded projects.

- EU Projects Highlighted: 87 EU research projects, 68 scientific institutions involved.

Objective 6: Organize high-quality outreach activities.

- Satisfaction Level: 60% gave the highest rating, no negative feedback.

Overall, the results indicate that the project successfully achieved its intended objectives and, in several cases, **exceeded the targets** initially set. The outcomes fully align with the project's mission to strengthen science communication, engage diverse and new audiences, and promote researchers' involvement in outreach activities.

DO YOU USUALLY PARTICIPATE IN SCIENCE EVENTS OR FESTIVALS?

Figure 14: Connection with science-festivals for participants of ERNs (2024 and 2025), Meet the Scientist Campaign, and Social inclusion through Science.

Source of data: participant surveys ($n=2,169$ for ERNs, $n=6,052$ for Meet the Scientists, $n= 86$ for Social Inclusion events).

The objective of reaching **new audiences** was clearly fulfilled, as demonstrated by the proportion of participants reporting that the project activities represented their first direct contact with a scientist (Figure 12). Notably, activities held in schools and in peripheral urban areas reached the highest shares of new audiences and participants with limited prior exposure to science, at **29%** and **33%**, respectively. ERN events also succeeded in reaching new publics, though to a lesser extent: **18%** of ERN participants stated that this was their first interaction with a scientist. Overall, however, ERN audiences tend to be more highly educated and more strongly connected to science than the general population.

The project also met its objective of engaging audiences with no prior experience of science festivals (Figure 14). In this case as well, the highest proportions were observed in activities carried out in peripheral areas (59% of participants reported never having attended a science festival) and in schools (42% of students stated they had never participated in a science festival before). While ERN audiences are generally more

accustomed to such events, 23% reported that they had never attended a science festival prior to ERN, indicating that the initiative was still effective in attracting new publics.

With regard to researcher participation, the project recorded a notably high involvement of women researchers: 69% of all participating researchers were female, a figure that exceeds the national average in Portugal, where women represent approximately 48% of the research workforce (Figure 15). This higher female representation was observed across all research areas and was not limited to traditionally female-dominated fields, such as the natural sciences, but also extended to areas historically characterized by lower female participation, including engineering and medical sciences.

Finally, large-scale events with high public attendance—such as the ERNs and their build-up activities—were those in which the proportion of researchers participating in outreach activities for the first time was highest (13%) (Figure XX). This proportion decreased to 8% in the Meet the Scientists activities and to 0% in the Social Inclusion through Science activities. These findings confirm the crucial role of ERNs and other large-scale public events in encouraging researchers to engage in science communication and outreach activities for the first time.

EU-EMBRACES RESEARCHER'S GENDER

EU-EMBRACES RESEARCHER'S AREA AND GENDER

Figure 15: Gender of reserchers participated in EU-EMBRACES activities: comparison with portugal distribution (top); distribution per research ares.

Source of data: researcher's survey (n=2,21); Gender in Portugal Researcher Area: A case study on European Leadership, 2024 Elsevier, <https://www.elsevier.com/insights/gender-and-diversity-in-research/portugal>; Scopus and NamSor.

7.2 Recommendations for future Edition

Overall, the tools used for data collection and impact evaluation performed well, and their effectiveness was satisfactory. The collaboration among venues to centralize data collection also proved successful and helped streamline the process.

However, one area for improvement is increasing the response rate for surveys directed at researchers, particularly for larger events like certain Build-Up and ERN activities. To address this, we recommend collecting survey responses on the event day itself, rather than postponing the request.

The strategy of providing small tokens to incentivize survey participation at large-scale events has proven successful. However, paper-based questionnaires still require significant time and human resources for digitization before they can be analyzed. Ideally, future editions could explore ways to encourage online survey completion—particularly for participants using smartphones—while maintaining the incentive of a token, provided either upon survey submission or with the support of a staff member actively encouraging responses. Experience has shown that simply displaying a QR

code without any in-person encouragement is not sufficient to achieve high response rates.

Future editions could also benefit from more systematic tracking of all researchers supported by EU funding, not only during the ERN but also in Researchers at School activities. Additionally, making certain fields in the event report forms mandatory or more explicit would reduce the need for time-consuming reconstruction of incomplete information, as experienced in previous editions.

Implementing these refinements would strengthen engagement with both participants and researchers and provide more comprehensive and reliable insights into the impact of large-scale events.

Appendix 1. Impact overview

Below is the **Impact Overview Table at Month 9** of the project, outlining its progress and impact so far. It is divided into **short-term** and **mid-term impact**:

- **Foreseen Impact** – Expected outcomes for the project as a whole.
- **State of the Art at M9** – Current progress based on collected data.
- **Additional Information** – Relevant contextual details, if applicable.

Long-term impacts are not included, as they require more time to assess and will be evaluated in later stages.

Appendix 2. Copies of Assessment Tools

9.1 Build-up event and ERN

Build-up events ERN 2024 – Activity Form (Organization)

This form is intended to gather information about activities carried out as pre-events for the European Researchers' Night in 2024 and 2025. A separate form must be completed for each event/activity.

The form should be completed by the organization responsible for the activity, ideally by someone directly involved in its implementation. The form fields refer to the activity, participants, the activity's impact on participants, and the scientists involved. It may be necessary to plan data collection in advance. Please submit the form with the information available, even if it is not possible to fill in all fields.

Filling out the form does not take much time. We thank you in advance for your collaboration.

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The Activity

- **Activity Title** *Required*
- **Date** *Required* (Month, day, year)
- **Location** *Required*
- **Duration**
- **Type of Activity** *Required*
- **Organizing Entity**

Participants

- **Number of Participants (approximate)** *Required*
- **Age Range of Participants**
- **Context(s) of Participants**
(e.g., school, families, migrant community, adults, children, etc.)

Scientists

- **Number of Scientists Involved** *Required*
- **Scientific Fields of the Scientists**

Impact of the Activity on Participants

- **Participants' Satisfaction with the Activity**

Rate from 1 (Very Dissatisfied) to 5 (Very Satisfied):

- **How was participants' satisfaction assessed?**

- Observation
- Surveys
- Written Comments
- Oral Comments
- Dotmocracy
- Post-it Wall
- Other (specify)

- **Was it possible to identify any impact or changes in participants? What changed?**

Examples:

- Participants who had never previously engaged with science spoke with a scientist for the first time.
- Participants learned that becoming a scientist is a possible career path in Portugal.
- Participants discovered previously unknown aspects of science.
- Scientists who had never interacted with the public before gained experience in public engagement.

Note: It is not always possible to provoke or identify changes.

- **Evidence of Change**

Include comments, testimonials, or observations that demonstrate the identified change. You may also add photographs of the event or other materials showcasing the activity's impact (e.g., dotmocracy, post-it wall, etc.).

- **Photographs**

Build-up events & ERN 2024 – Survey (Scientists)

This questionnaire is intended to evaluate scientists' perceptions of the event. The responses are personal.

Completing this questionnaire should take no more than 3 minutes.

Participation is voluntary. You may decline to complete it or abandon it at any time.

Your responses will always remain confidential. They will be submitted to a Google Forms link that only the project researchers can access. Google Forms does not require registration and does not collect identifiable data such as IP addresses. No one will be able to identify you or know whether you participated in the survey.

If you have any questions at any time regarding the study or its procedures, please contact us at **sci@itqb.unl.pt**.

This event is part of the European Researchers' Night 2024, organized under the EU-EMBRACES project.

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ELECTRONIC

CONSENT:

Please select your choice below. You may print a copy of this consent for your records.

By clicking "I Agree," you confirm that:

- You have read the information above;
- You are participating voluntarily;
- You are 18 years or older.
 - **I Agree**
 - **I Do Not Agree (Exit Survey)**

The activity

- **Event or Activity Title**
- **Date** (Month, Day, Year)
- **Event Location**
- **Organizing Entity**
- **Did the event take place during the European Researchers' Night?**
 - Yes
 - No
- **Age**
 - Under 35
 - 35–44
 - 45–54
 - 55–64

- Over 65
- **Gender**
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to say
 - Other: [Specify]
- **Scientific Field of Activity**
 - Exact Sciences
 - Natural Sciences
 - Engineering and Technology
 - Medical and Health Sciences
 - Agricultural Sciences
 - Social Sciences
 - Humanities
 - Other: [Specify]
- **Professional Category / Relationship with Science**
 - Master's Student
 - Ph.D. Student
 - Postdoctoral Researcher (with fellowship or fixed-term contract)
 - Career Researcher or Academic Staff
 - Other: [Specify]
- **Have you participated in science communication activities like this one (direct interaction with the public) before?**
 - No, this was my first time
 - Yes, I participate occasionally
 - Yes, I participate regularly (2–4 times per year)
 - Yes, I participate frequently (5 or more times per year)
- **How would you describe the people (non-scientists) you interacted with during this activity?**
- **Do you feel your participation in this activity was rewarding for you? If so, in what way?**
- **From your perspective, what were the positive aspects of this activity?**
- **From your perspective, what challenges did you encounter, or what aspects could be improved?**
- **Additional Comments:**

ERN 2024 – Activity Form (Organization)

This form is intended to gather information about the 2024 and 2025 European Researchers' Night event. A separate form must be filled out for each night.

The responsibility for completing the form lies with the organizing entity of the activity.

The fields in this form refer to the description of the activity, the participants, the scientists involved, and the impact of the activity on the participants. It may be necessary to plan the collection of this information in advance. Please submit the form with the available data, even if not all fields can be completed.

Filling out the form is quick and simple. We thank you in advance for your cooperation.

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The Activity

- **Activity Title**
- **Date**(Month, day, year)
- **Location**
- **Duration**
- **Type** of activity

Participants

- Approximate number of participants
- Age range of participants
- Context(s) of participants
(e.g., school, families, migrant community, adults, children, etc.)

Scientists

- Number of scientists involved
- Scientific areas of the scientists

Impact of the activity on participants

- Participant satisfaction with the activity (if applicable)
Where 1 means very dissatisfied and 5 means very satisfied
- How was participant satisfaction measured?
 - Observation
 - Surveys
 - Written comments
 - Oral comments
 - Dotmocracy
 - Post-it wall
 - Other...

- Was any impact or change identified in the participants? What changed?
For example:

There were participants who had never had prior contact with science, who spoke with a scientist for the first time, who were unaware that being a scientist was a possible career in Portugal, or who were unaware of certain aspects of science.

There were scientists who had never interacted with the public before...

Note: It is not always possible to provoke or identify changes.

Evidence of change

Include comments, testimonies, or observations that demonstrate the change. You may also add photographs of the event or others that show the impact of the activity (dotmocracy, post-it wall, etc.).

Photographs

ERN 2024 – Satisfaction Survey (Participants)

The following questions aim to assess your perception of this event and help us characterize the audience that joined us for this European Researchers' Night using statistical indicators.

The answers are personal, please respond based on your own experience. Completing this survey should not take more than 5 minutes. Participation is voluntary, and you

can refuse to answer or exit the survey at any point. Your responses will be extremely useful in improving your experience, as well as that of other participants, in future activities. We guarantee that your answers will always remain confidential.

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Contact: If you have any questions at any time regarding the study or the procedures, you can contact us via sci@itqb.unl.pt.

Consent: By agreeing, you indicate that you have read the above information and are participating voluntarily.

I agree

I do not agree

Location of the ERN

Where did the European Researchers' Night you are referring to take place?

- CCV Alcalena
- CCV Braga
- CCV Bragança
- CCV Estremoz
- CCV Lagos
- CCV Lisboa
- CCV Vila Nova de Foz Côa
- Oeiras
- Porto

Share your impressions with us!

- **Rate your level of satisfaction with the event from 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied).**
- **What did you like the most?**
- **What could be improved?**
- **I didn't know and I found out that...**

Now, help us get to know the audience who joined us at this event by providing some information about yourself.

- **Age**
 - Under 15 years
 - 15-24 years
 - 25-34 years
 - 35-44 years
 - 45-54 years
 - 55-64 years
 - 65 years or older
- **Gender**
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to answer
 - Other
- **Postal Code** (if you reside outside Portugal, you can indicate the country)
- **Level of education**
 - Primary education - 1st cycle
 - Primary education - 2nd cycle
 - Primary education - 3rd cycle
 - Secondary education
 - Post-secondary education
 - Bachelor's degree
 - Master's degree
 - PhD
 - Other
- **Professional status**
 - Student
 - Employed
 - Unemployed
 - Homemaker
 - Retired
 - Other
- **Mother's level of education**
 - No schooling
 - Primary education
 - Secondary education

- Higher education
- Other.
- **Was this the first time you interacted with a scientist?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - **Do you usually participate in science events or festivals?**
 - Never participated before
 - Yes, occasionally
 - Yes, frequently
- **What is your connection to science?**
 - I have no direct connection to science
 - I have friends or family who are scientists
 - I have training in a scientific area
 - I work or have worked in science
 - Other

9.2 Meet the Scientists campaign

Meet the Scientists – Session Form (Teachers)

This form is designed to collect information about the Meet the Scientist sessions within the framework of the European Researchers' Night in 2024 and 2025. A separate form should be filled out for each session.

The form should be completed by the teacher who attended the session. The fields in the form relate to the activity, the scientists, the participants, and the effect of the activity on the participants. It may be necessary to plan the collection of this information in advance. Please submit the form with the available information, even if not all fields can be completed.

The completion of the form does not take much time. We appreciate your collaboration in advance.

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Format

- Online
- In-person

If the session was in-person, please indicate the location where it took place:

Session Theme

- Horizon Europe Mission addressed in the session (if applicable):
 - Beating Cancer
 - Tackling Climate Change
 - Developing the Cities of the Future
 - Ensuring Soil and Food Health
 - Protecting the Oceans
 - Not applicable

Duration of the session
Session Description

Please briefly describe what the session consisted of, including the socioeconomic context of the school and the habits of interaction (or lack thereof) with scientists. Describe the conditions that influenced the interaction, facilitating or hindering it. (If the meeting was in-person, detail the location, available space, and materials used, such as computers or laboratory equipment. If it was online, comment on the participation dynamics, tools used, and relevant logistical aspects.)

Participants
Number of students (approximate)
Educational level

- Primary Education (1st cycle)
- Primary Education (2nd cycle)
- Primary Education (3rd cycle)
- Secondary Education
- Other

Scientists
Number of scientists involved

Scientific area of the scientist(s)

Please rate the following statements according to your level of agreement (agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree, not applicable):

- The scientist(s) adapted their speech to the age/knowledge of the students.
- The scientist(s) sought to promote the participation of the students.
- The scientist(s) showed interest in the students' questions/opinions.

Effect of the session on the participants

During the session, the students were:

- Bored
- Distracted
- Attentive
- Enthusiastic
- Participative
- Other...

Was it possible to identify any impact/change in the participants? What changed?

For example: did students talk to a scientist for the first time, learn something new, discover a scientific career, or form an opinion on a new topic?

Note: It is not always possible to provoke or identify changes.

Evidence(s) of change

Include here any comments, testimonies, or observations that demonstrate the change observed.

You can also add photographs from the event or others that highlight the impact of the activity.

Note: If you wish to include photographs, make sure to ask for permission to take pictures, ensure that no faces are visible (photograph from behind), and that no student is identifiable.

Other observations/comments that can help us assess the impact of the session on participants (and scientists)

Photographs

Meet the Scientists – Survey (Students)

This questionnaire aims to evaluate your perception of this session and help us characterize the audience who participated in this event using statistical indicators.

Your responses are personal, so please answer based on your own experience. Participation is voluntary, and you can choose not to answer or leave the survey at any time. Your responses will always remain confidential. Completing the questionnaire will take no more than 5 minutes, and your contributions will be extremely valuable for improving both your experience and that of other participants in future activities.

This event is part of the European Researchers' Night 2024, organized under the EU-EMBRACES project.

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Contact.

If you have any questions about the study or procedures, you can contact us at any time at sci@itqb.unl.pt.

Consent.

By agreeing, you indicate that you have read the above information and are voluntarily participating.

- I agree
- I do not agree

Share your impressions of this session with us.

Rate your level of satisfaction with the session from 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied).:

**What did you like most?
What do you think could be improved?
I didn't know, but in this session, I learned...**

Help us better understand the audience that joined this event through statistical indicators.

Grade level

- 7th grade
- 8th grade
- 9th grade
- 10th grade
- 11th grade
- 12th grade

School

Gender

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other...

Your mother's education level

- No formal education
- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Higher education
- Other...

Was this the first time you directly interacted with a scientist?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Was there anything that surprised you during this interaction? What was it?

Do you think you could become a scientist?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Have you participated in other science-related activities (outside of school)?

- No, never
- Yes, occasionally
- Yes, regularly

Meet the Scientists – Survey (Scientists)

This questionnaire aims to assess the perception of scientists about the "Meet the Scientist" event within the scope of the EU-EMBRACES project. The responses are personal. Completing this questionnaire should take no more than 5 minutes.

Participation in this questionnaire is voluntary. You may refuse to participate or discontinue at any point.

Your responses will always remain confidential. The responses will be sent to a Google Forms link, which only project researchers can access. Google Forms does not require registration or collect identifying data, such as IP addresses. No one will be able to identify your identity or know whether you participated in the survey.

CONTACT

If you have any questions at any time regarding the study or procedures, you can contact us at sci@itqb.unl.pt.

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ELECTRONIC

CONSENT:

Please select your choice below. You may print a copy of this consent for your records.

By clicking "I Agree," you indicate that:

- You have read the information above;
- You are participating voluntarily;
- You are 18 years of age or older.

I Agree

I Do Not Agree (leave survey)

Age

- Under 35
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- Over 65

Gender

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to answer
- Other...

Field of Scientific Activity

- Exact Sciences
- Natural Sciences
- Engineering and Technology
- Medical and Health Sciences
- Agricultural Sciences
- Social Sciences
- Humanities
- Other...

Professional Category

- Master's Student

- PhD Student
 - Doctoral Researcher with a fellowship or fixed-term contract
 - Career Researcher or Professor
 - Other...
-

Have you previously participated in science communication activities of this type (direct contact with the public)?

- No, this was my first time
- Yes, I participate occasionally
- Yes, I participate regularly (2-4 times per year)
- Yes, I participate regularly (5 or more times per year)

Type of participation in the session:

- Online
- In-person

How would you describe the students you interacted with in this session?

Do you feel your participation in this session was rewarding for you? If so, how?

From your perspective, what positive aspects would you highlight?

From your perspective, what challenges did you encounter or aspects that could be improved?

Other observations/comments

9.3 Participatory debates

Participatory Debates – Session Form (Organization)

This form is designed to collect information about the debates organized as part of the European Researchers' Night in 2024 and 2025. A separate form should be filled out for each session.

The form should be completed by the organization responsible for the activity, ideally by the main facilitator of the debate or someone who was present during the session. The fields cover information about the activity, participants, the effect of the activity on participants, and the scientists involved. It may be necessary to plan in advance to gather the required information. Please submit the form with the available information, even if not all fields can be completed.

Completing this form is quick and straightforward. Thank you in advance for your collaboration.

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-
- **Session Date** (Month, day, year)
 - **Location**
 - **Session Topic**
 - **Horizon Europe Mission covered during the session (if applicable):**
 - Beating Cancer
 - Fighting Climate Change
 - Developing Future Cities
 - Ensuring Soil Health and Food Security
 - Protecting the Oceans
 - Not applicable
 - **Duration**
 - **Brief Description of the Session**
(Include information such as the social context of the school, room conditions that might facilitate or hinder participation, presence of teachers, and any other relevant aspects...)

Participants

- **Number of Students (approximate)**
- **Educational Level**
 - Lower Secondary Education (3rd Cycle)
 - Upper Secondary Education

- Other
- **What measures were taken to attract underrepresented audiences to this type of event, such as students from disadvantaged communities and/or minorities, and to ensure diversity in gender, age, and socioeconomic background within the group?**
- **Was this goal achieved? To what extent?**
(Describe the type of audience and the diversity in terms of gender, age, and socioeconomic background.)

Scientists

(Description optional)

- **Number of Scientists Involved**
 - 1
 - 2
 - 3 or more
- **Scientific Area of the Scientists**
- **Was gender equality achieved among scientists and other experts?**
- **Please rate the following statements based on your level of agreement:**
 - The scientist(s) adapted their language to the age/knowledge level of the students.
 - The scientist(s) encouraged student participation.
 - The scientist(s) showed interest in the students' questions/opinions.

Effect of the Session on Participants

To answer the following questions: record the number of positive responses to the questions asked at the end of the debate, out of the total number of participants.

*(For example, assuming 16 students participated:
 Who knew that the European Commission had defined 5 missions? 9/16
 Who had previously participated in a debate? 5/16
 Who had thought about the topic under discussion before? 14/16
 Etc.)*

- **Who knew that the European Commission had defined 5 missions?**
- **Who had previously participated in a debate?**
- **Who had thought about the topic under discussion before?**
- **Which missions have scientists working in Portugal? (Indicate the response for each mission.)**

- **During the session, students were:**
 - Bored
 - Distracted
 - Attentive
 - Enthusiastic
 - Participative
 - Other...
- **Was it possible to identify any impact/change in the participants? What changed?**

(For example, students may have spoken to a scientist for the first time, learned something new, discovered a scientific career path, or formed an opinion on a new topic...)

Note: It is not always possible to provoke or identify changes.
- **Evidence of Change**

(Include comments, testimonials, or observations that demonstrate the changes identified. You may also add photographs or other evidence of the activity's impact.)

Note: If you want to include photographs, make sure to ask for permission to photograph, ensure the images do not show faces (photograph from behind), and that no students are recognizable.
- **Other observations/comments to help us assess the session's impact on participants (and on scientists)**
- **Photographs**

Participatory Debates – Survey (Students)

This questionnaire aims to evaluate your perception of this session and help us better understand the audience that participated in this debate on Horizon Europe missions through statistical indicators.

The answers are personal, so please respond based on your own experience. Participation is voluntary, and you can choose not to respond or exit the survey at any time. Your responses will always remain confidential. Completing the survey will take no more than 5 minutes, and your contributions will be highly valuable to improve both your experience and that of other participants in future activities.

This event is part of the European Researchers' Night 2024, organized under the EU-EMBRACES project.

The EU-EMBRACES project is funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the positions of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the funding authority can be held responsible for them.

Contact:

If you have any questions about the study or procedures, you can contact us at any time at **sci@itqb.unl.pt**.

Consent

By agreeing, you indicate that you have read the information above and that you are voluntarily participating.

- I agree
- I do not agree

Share your impressions about this debate

- **Rate your level of satisfaction with the session** (from 1 not satisfied to 5 completely satisfied)
- **What did you enjoy the most?**
- **What did you dislike or think could be improved?**
- **Do you feel that your opinion was important in the conclusions of the debate?**
 - Yes
 - Maybe, it's hard to tell
 - I don't feel that my opinion was considered
 - I did not have the opportunity to share my opinion
 - I had the opportunity to share my opinion, but I chose not to
 - Other...
- **I didn't know, but in this session I learned that...**

Help us better understand the audience that participated in these debates through statistical indicators

- **School Year**

- 7th grade
- 8th grade
- 9th grade
- 10th grade
- 11th grade
- 12th grade
- **School**
- **Gender**
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to answer
 - Other...
- **Your Mother's Education Level**
 - No education
 - Basic education
 - Secondary education
 - Higher education
 - Other...
- **Was this the first time you directly interacted with a scientist?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - I don't know
- **Did anything surprise you during this interaction? If yes, what?**
- **Do you think you could become a scientist?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - I don't know
- **Have you participated in other science-related activities (outside of school)?**
 - No, never
 - Yes, occasionally
 - Yes, regularly

Participatory Debates (Scientists)

This questionnaire aims to evaluate scientists' perceptions of the Participatory Debates under the EU-EMBRACES project.

The responses are personal. Completing this questionnaire should take no more than 5 minutes.

Participation in this questionnaire is voluntary. You may refuse to participate or exit the survey at any point.

Your responses will always remain confidential. The answers will be submitted to a link in GoogleForms accessible only to the project's researchers. GoogleForms does not require registration or collect identifying data such as IP addresses. No one will be able to identify your identity or know whether or not you participated in the survey.

CONTACT

If you have any questions about the study or procedures, you can contact us at any time via sci@itqb.unl.pt.

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ELECTRONIC

CONSENT

Please select your choice below. You may print a copy of this consent for your records. By clicking "I Agree," you indicate that:

- You have read the information above.
- You are voluntarily participating.
- You are 18 years or older.
- I Agree
- I Do Not Agree (exit survey)

-
- **Age:**
 - Under 35 years

- 35–44 years
 - 45–54 years
 - 55–64 years
 - Over 65 years
 - **Gender:**
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to answer
 - Other...
 - **Field of Scientific Activity:**
 - Exact Sciences
 - Natural Sciences
 - Engineering and Technology
 - Medical and Health Sciences
 - Agricultural Sciences
 - Social Sciences
 - Humanities
 - Other...
 - **Professional Category:**
 - Master’s Student
 - PhD Student
 - Postdoctoral Researcher with a Fellowship or Fixed-Term Contract
 - Career Researcher or Lecturer
 - Other...
-
- **Have you previously participated in science communication activities of this type (direct interaction with the public)?**
 - No, it was my first time
 - Yes, I participate occasionally
 - Yes, I participate regularly (2–4 times per year)
 - Yes, I participate regularly (5 or more times per year)
 - **How would you describe the students with whom you interacted in this session?**
 - **Do you feel your participation in this session was rewarding for you? If yes, please explain how.**
 - **From the perspective of your participation, highlight the positive aspects you would emphasize.**

- **From the perspective of your participation, highlight challenges you encountered or aspects that could be improved.**
- **Other observations/comments:**

9.4 Social inclusion through science and technology

Activities and Workshops in Neighborhoods – Activity Form (Organizers)

This form is designed to gather information about the activities and workshops conducted in neighborhoods as part of the "Social Inclusion through Science" program. One form should be completed for each event/activity.

The form should be filled out by the entity responsible for the activity, ideally by someone directly involved in its implementation. The fields in the form pertain to the activity, the participants, the impact of the activity on participants, and the scientists involved. It may be necessary to plan the collection of this information in advance. Please submit the form with the available information, even if it is not possible to fill out all fields.

Filling out the form does not require much time. We thank you in advance for your collaboration.

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The Activity

- **Activity Title**
- **Date** (*Month, day, year*)
- **Location**
- **Duration**
- **Type of Activity**
- **Organizing Entity**

- **Horizon Europe Mission addressed in the session (if applicable)**
 - Beating Cancer
 - Fighting Climate Change
 - Building the Cities of the Future
 - Ensuring Soil and Food Health
 - Protecting the Oceans
 - Not applicable
 - **Did you receive support from any neighborhood structure or person/entity working in the neighborhood?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - **If yes, can you specify the type of entity or structure that provided support?**
 - **Was it important for the success of the event?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - Not applicable
-

Participants

- **Number of Participants (approximate)**
 - **Age Range of Participants**
 - **Context(s) of Participants** (*e.g., school, families, migrant community, adults, children, etc.*)
 - **Compared to other activities organized, was it more difficult to attract participants?**
 - Yes
 - No
-

Scientists

- **Number of Scientists Involved**
- **Scientific Areas of the Scientists**
- **Compared to other activities organized, was it more difficult to recruit scientists?**
 - Yes
 - No

Impact of the Activity on Participants

- **Participants' Satisfaction with the Activity** (*Where 1 means Very Dissatisfied and 5 means Very Satisfied*)
- **How was participants' satisfaction assessed?**
 - Observation
 - Surveys
 - Written Comments
 - Oral Comments
 - Dotmocracy
 - Post-it Wall
 - Questions with raised-hand votes
 - Other...
- **Was it possible to identify any impact or change on the participants? What changed?** (*For example:*
 - *Participants who had never been exposed to science before, spoke with a scientist for the first time, learned that being a scientist is a viable career in Portugal, or discovered new aspects of science.*
 - *Scientists who had never interacted with the public before...*
Note: It is not always possible to provoke or identify changes.)
- **Evidence of Change**
(*Include comments, testimonials, or observations that demonstrate the change observed. You may also add photos of the event or other evidence of the activity's impact, such as dotmocracy, post-it wall, etc.*)
- **Photographs**

Activities and Workshops in Neighborhoods – Satisfaction Survey (Participants)

The following questions aim to evaluate your perception of this event and help us better understand the audience that joined us through statistical indicators.

Your responses are personal, so please answer based on your own experience. Completing this questionnaire should not take more than 5 minutes. Participation is voluntary, and you may choose not to answer or leave the survey at any time. Your answers will be extremely helpful in improving your experience, as well as that of other participants, in future activities. We guarantee that your responses will always remain confidential.

This survey is part of the EU-EMBRACES project funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Contact

If you have any questions about the study or procedures at any time, you can contact us at sci@itqb.unl.pt.

Consent

By agreeing, you indicate that you have read the above information and are participating voluntarily.

I agree

I do not agree

Share your impressions with us!

- **Rate your level of satisfaction with the event from 1 (not satisfied at all) to 5 (completely satisfied).**
 - **What did you like the most?**
 - **What could be improved?**
 - **What did you learn that you did not know before?**
 - **Was there anything that surprised you?**
-

Now, help us learn more about the audience that joined us for this event by providing some information about yourself.

Age

- Under 15 years old

- 15–24 years old

- 25–34 years old
- 35–44 years old
- 45–54 years old
- 55–64 years old
- 65 years or older

Gender

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to answer
- Other

Postal Code (if living outside Portugal, you can indicate the country)

Level of Education

- Primary education - 1st cycle
- Primary education - 2nd cycle
- Primary education - 3rd cycle
- Secondary education
- Post-secondary education
- Bachelor's degree

- Master's degree
- Doctorate
- Other

Employment Status

- Student
- Employed
- Unemployed
- Homemaker
- Retired
- Other

Your mother's level of education

- No formal education
- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Higher education
- Other

Was this your first time interacting with a scientist?

- Yes
- No

Do you often participate in science events or festivals?

- I had never participated before
- Yes, occasionally
- Yes, frequently

What is your connection to science?

- I have no direct connection to science
- I have friends or family members who are scientists
- I have training in a scientific field
- I work or have worked in science
- Other

Activities and Workshops in Neighborhoods – Survey (Scientists)

This questionnaire aims to evaluate scientists' perceptions of this event. Responses are personal.

Completing this questionnaire should take no more than 3 minutes.

Participation is voluntary. You may choose not to complete it or abandon it at any time.

Your responses will always remain confidential. They will be submitted through a Google Forms link, which is accessible only to the project researchers. Google Forms does not require registration or collect identifying data, such as IP addresses. No one will be able to identify your identity or know whether you participated in the survey.

If you have any questions about the study or its procedures, you may contact us at sci@itqb.unl.pt.

This event is part of the European Researchers' Night 2024, organized within the scope of the EU-EMBRACES project.

The EU-EMBRACES project is funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the positions of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the funding authority can be held responsible for them.

ELECTRONIC

CONSENT

Please select your choice below. You may print a copy of this consent form for your records. By clicking "I Agree," you indicate that:

- You have read the information provided above;
- You are participating voluntarily;
- You are 18 years of age or older.

*

I Agree

I Do Not Agree (exit survey)

Event or Activity Title / Date / Organization / Location

Age

- Under 35 years old
- 35–44 years old
- 45–54 years old
- 55–64 years old
- Over 65 years old

Gender

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to answer
- Other

Scientific Field

- Exact Sciences
- Natural Sciences
- Engineering and Technology
- Medical and Health Sciences
- Agricultural Sciences
- Social Sciences
- Humanities
- Other

Professional Category / Relationship with Science

- Master's Student
- PhD Student
- Postdoctoral Researcher with a Fellowship or Fixed-term Contract
- Career Researcher or Lecturer
- Other

Have you previously participated in science communication activities of this type (direct interaction with the public)?

- No, this was my first time
- Yes, I occasionally participate
- Yes, I regularly participate (2–4 times per year)
- Yes, I frequently participate (5 or more times per year)

How would you describe the people you interacted with during this activity?

Do you feel that your participation in this activity was rewarding? If yes, in what way?

From the perspective of your participation, highlight the positive aspects of this activity.

From the perspective of your participation, mention the challenges you faced or aspects that could be improved.

Was there anything that surprised you about the target audience?

Additional Comments

Activities and Workshops in TEIP Schools – Session Form (Teachers)

This form is intended to collect information about the "Meet the Scientists" sessions organized as part of the European Researchers' Night in 2024 and 2025. A separate form should be completed for each session.

The form is to be completed by the teacher who attended the session. It includes fields related to the activity, the scientists, the participants, and the impact of the activity on the participants. It may be necessary to plan the collection of this information in advance. Please submit the form with the available information, even if some fields cannot be completed.

Filling out this form does not take much time. Thank you in advance for your cooperation.

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-
- **Location of the activity**
 - **Session topic**
 - **Horizon Europe mission addressed in the session (if applicable):**

- Beating cancer
- Combating climate change
- Building the cities of the future
- Ensuring soil health and food security
- Protecting the oceans
- Not applicable
- **Duration of the session**
- **Session description**

Briefly explain the nature of the session, mentioning the socioeconomic context of the school and any established (or absent) habits of interaction with scientists.

Describe the conditions that influenced the interaction, either facilitating or hindering it. (For example, detail the venue, available space, and materials used, such as computers or laboratory equipment.)

Participants

- **Approximate number of students**
 - **Educational level:**
 - Primary School (1st cycle)
 - Primary School (2nd cycle)
 - Primary School (3rd cycle)
 - Secondary School
 - Other
-

Scientists

- **Number of scientists involved:**
- **Scientific field(s) of the scientist(s)**
- **Rate the following statements based on your level of agreement:**
(Agree / Neither agree nor disagree / Disagree / Not applicable)
 - The scientist(s) successfully adapted their communication to the students' age/knowledge level.
 - The scientist(s) made an effort to encourage student participation.
 - The scientist(s) demonstrated interest in the students' questions and opinions.

Effect of the session on participants

- During the session, the students were:
 - Bored
 - Distracted
 - Attentive
 - Enthusiastic
 - Engaged
 - Other...
- **Was it possible to identify any impact or change in the participants? If so, what changed?**

(For example: Some students spoke with a scientist for the first time, learned something new, discovered a scientific career, or formed an opinion on a new topic.)

Note: It is not always possible to provoke or identify changes.

- **Evidence of change**

Include comments, testimonials, or observations that demonstrate the change observed.

You may also attach photographs or other materials that highlight the impact of the activity.

Note: If including photographs, ensure you have permission to take them. Photographs should not include identifiable faces (e.g., taken from behind) or any recognizable details of students.

- **Additional observations/comments**

Share any other comments that may help us assess the impact of the session on the participants (and the scientists).

- **Photographs**

Activities and Workshops in TEIP Schools – Survey (Students)

This questionnaire aims to evaluate your perception of this session and help us better understand the audience who participated in this event through statistical indicators.

Your responses are personal, so please answer based on your own experience. Participation is voluntary, and you can choose not to answer or exit the survey at any time. Your responses will always remain confidential. Completing the questionnaire will take no more than 5 minutes, and your input is highly valuable to improving your experience and that of other participants in future activities.

This event is part of the European Researchers' Night 2024, organized under the EU-EMBRACES project.

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Contact

If you have any questions about the study or its procedures, you can contact us at any time at **sci@itqb.unl.pt**.

Consent

By agreeing, you confirm that you have read the above information and that you are participating voluntarily.

- **I agree**
- **I do not agree**

Share your impressions of this session.

- **:Rate your level of satisfaction with the session from 1 (not satisfied at all) to 5 (completely satisfied).**
- **What did you like the most?**
- **What do you think could be improved?**
- **Something I didn't know but learned during this session...**

Help us better understand the audience who joined this event through statistical indicators.

- **Grade**
 - 7th grade

- 8th grade
- 9th grade
- 10th grade
- 11th grade
- 12th grade
- **School**
- **Gender**
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to say
 - Other...
- **Your mother's level of education**
 - No formal education
 - Primary education
 - Secondary education
 - Higher education
 - Other...
- **Was this your first time interacting directly with a scientist?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - I'm not sure
- **Was there anything that surprised you about this interaction? What?**
- **Do you think you could become a scientist?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - I'm not sure
- **Have you participated in other science-related activities (outside school)?**
 - No, never
 - Yes, sometimes
 - Yes, regularly

Activities and Workshops in Schools – Survey (Scientists)

This questionnaire aims to evaluate scientists' perception of the "Meet the Scientist" event within the scope of the EU-EMBRACES project.

The answers are personal.

Completing this questionnaire should take no more than 5 minutes.

Participation in this survey is voluntary. You may choose not to participate in this survey or leave it at any point.

Your responses will always be confidential. The answers will be sent to a link on Google Forms, which only the project researchers have access to. Google Forms does not require registration or collect identifying data such as IP addresses. No one will be able to identify your identity or know whether you participated in the survey.

CONTACT

If you have any questions at any time regarding the study or the procedures, you can contact us at sci@itqb.unl.pt.

The EU-EMBRACES project is funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the positions of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the funding authority can be held responsible for them.

ELECTRONIC

CONSENT:

Please select your choice below. You may print a copy of this consent for your records. By clicking "I Agree," you confirm that:

- You have read the above information.
- You are participating voluntarily.
- You are 18 years of age or older.
- **I agree**
- **I do not agree (exit survey)**

-
- **Age**
 - Under 35 years
 - 35-44 years
 - 45-54 years
 - 55-64 years
 - Over 65 years
 - **Gender**
 - Male
 - Female

- Prefer not to respond
- Other...
- **Field of Scientific Activity**
 - Exact Sciences
 - Natural Sciences
 - Engineering and Technology
 - Medical and Health Sciences
 - Agricultural Sciences
 - Social Sciences
 - Humanities
 - Other...
- **Professional Category**
 - Master's Student
 - Doctoral Student
 - Doctorate holder with grant or fixed-term contract
 - Career Researcher or Professor
 - Other...
- **Had you previously participated in science communication activities of this type (direct contact with the public)?**
 - No, it was my first time
 - Yes, I participate occasionally
 - Yes, I participate regularly (2-4 times per year)
 - Yes, I participate frequently (5 or more times per year)
- **Type of participation in the session:**
 - Online
 - In-person
- **How would you describe the students you interacted with during this session?**
- **Do you feel your participation in this session was rewarding for you? If so, in what way?**
- **From your perspective, what positive aspects would you highlight from your participation?**
- **From your perspective, what challenges did you encounter or aspects that could be improved?**
- **Was there anything that surprised you regarding the target audience?**
- **Other observations/comments**

9.5 Youth Ambassadors Program

Youth Ambassadors NEI Program – Session Form (organizing entity)

This form is intended to collect information about the Youth Ambassadors Program within the framework of the European Researchers' Night 2024–2025.

The form is to be completed by the organizing entity. The fields in the form relate to the activity, the participants, and the activity's impact on participants (including science communication outputs). Please submit the form with the information available, even if it is not possible to complete all fields.

Filling out the form does not require much time. We thank you in advance for your collaboration.

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General Information

- Where did the science communication workshop take place?
- Duration of the session
- Description of the session

Please briefly explain the purpose of the session, the topics covered, and the challenges presented to the students.

Participants

- Number of students
- Educational level:
 - Middle School (3rd cycle)
 - High School
 - Other

Facilitators

- Briefly describe who facilitated the session (e.g., communication office staff, scientists, specialists).

Impact of the session on participants

- During the session, students appeared:
 - Bored
 - Distracted
 - Attentive
 - Enthusiastic
 - Participative
 - Other:_____

- Do you consider that the main objectives of the workshop (improving project communication, adapting to different audiences, preparing pitches, etc.) were achieved? To what extent?
- What concrete changes did you observe in the students after participating (e.g., increased confidence, improved summarizing skills, greater creativity)?
You may include comments, testimonials, or observations illustrating these changes. You may also add photographs from the event or other images showing the impact of the activity.
Note: *If including photographs, ensure that permission has been obtained, avoid capturing faces (photograph from behind), and ensure that no student is recognizable.*
- How do you evaluate the outputs delivered by participants during the workshop?
- Pictures